

ENTRUST

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D5.2 ENTRUST Continuous Authorization, Trust Management, Monitoring Mechanisms and Trust Evidence Collection

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Abstract	<p>D5.2 is dedicated to the description of the final Blockchain Infrastructure of ENTRUST, which is responsible for enabling the secure data management in medical domain organisations. Specifically, we provide the final version of the ENTRUST Blockchain architecture and all participating components, as well as all Blockchain-related action workflows, namely the authentication, onboarding and enrolment of CMDs, the construction of the required crypto primitives, and re-establishment of trust. We also detailed the final versions of the smart contracts pertaining to application data, attestation data, and trust policies, and we investigated how the introduction of inheritance can increase efficiency in the transition from device-level to domain-level actions. The final version of the Security Context Broker was described, as well as its role in the positioning of advanced crypto in the context of ENTRUST, namely Attribute-Based Access Control and Attribute-Based Signcryption. Details on the final version of the tracing capabilities of ENTRUST were also provided for both High-end and Low-end devices. Finally, benchmarking results were provided for all aforementioned functionalities, and the results set the scene for the evaluation of ENTRUST in the context of the use cases, to be documented in D6.2.</p>		
Keywords	Blockchain, Inheritance, Smart Contracts, Tracing, Benchmarking, Attribute-Based Access Control, Attribute-Based Signcryption		

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SEN	Sensitive, confidential to ENTRUST project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting
ABAC	Attribute-based Access Control
ABE	Attribute-based Encryption
ABS	Attribute-based Signatures
ACL	Access Control List
AK	Attestation Key
AOO	Actions on Objectives
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
ATT&CK	Adversarial Tactics, techniques & Common Knowledge
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
C2	Command and Control
CA	Certification Authority
CEGAR	Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement
CFA	Control-Flow Attestation
CIV	Code Integrity Validation
CMD	Connected Medical Device
CPSs	Cyber-Physical Systems
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
DDoS	Distributed Denial-of-Service attacks
DDRV	Distributed and Decentralized Runtime Verification
DFG	Data Flow Diagram
DID	Domain Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DoS	Denial of Service
DT	Digital Twin
EMTs	Emergency Medical Technicians
ENISA	European Network and Information Security Agency
FES	Feel Emotion Sensor
FL	Federated Learning
FV	Formal Verification
FW	Firmware
HDOs	Healthcare Delivery Organizations
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HRV	Hardware-supported Runtime Verification
ICT	Information and Communications Technology

IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoC	Indicator of Compromise
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LTL	Linear Temporal Logic
MD	Medical Device
MDR	Medical Devices Regulation
MDSW	Medical Device Software
mHealth	Mobile health
MISP	Malware Information Sharing Platform
MITM	Man-In-The-Middle
ML	Machine Learning
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Descriptions
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OSN	Online Social Networks
PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication System
PHG	Tellu Personal Health Gateway
PMS	Patient Monitoring Systems
PUF	Physical Unclonable Function
QMS	Quality Management System
QoS	Quality of Service
RA	Risk Assessment
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
RoT	Root-of-Trust
RPMS	Remote Patient Monitoring Systems
RTL	Required Level of Trustworthiness
SA	Static Analysis
SBOM	Software Bill of Material
SDL	Secure Development Lifecycle
SL	Subjective Logic
SMT	Satisfiability Modulo Theories
SoS	System of Systems
SPLC	Secure Product Life Cycle
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
STRIDE	Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Denial of Service and Elevation of Privilege
SUT	System Under Test
SW	Software

SWaP	Size, Weight, and Power
TAR	Trust Assessment Request
TARA	Threat Agent Risk Assessment
TC	Trusted Component
TDE	Trust Decision Engine
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TI	Threat Intelligence
TLEE	Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine
TM	Threat Modelling
TMM	Trust Model Manager
TOE	Target of Evaluation
TSM	Trust Sources Manager
TTP	Tactics, Techniques and Procedures
UID	Unique Initial Identification
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VC	Verifiable Credential
VP	Verifiable Presentation
YANG	Yet Another Next Generation

Executive Summary

The core target of ENTRUST is to *enhance the capability of medical organisations to provide reliable healthcare services by ensuring that the trustworthiness level of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs), as well as the system as a whole, remains at an acceptable level.* To achieve this, ENTRUST designs and implements a holistic security framework, which aims to provide operational assurance to CMDs throughout their operational lifecycle, leveraging a variety of security and trust enablers. At the core of this process lies the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** of ENTRUST, which aims to ensure that the trustworthiness level of CMDs remains at an acceptable level, by computing their **Actual Trust Level (ATL)** dynamically during runtime and comparing it to their **Required Trust Level (RTL)**. In this process, the **Blockchain Infrastructure** of ENTRUST is a core component, as its inherent characteristics of **de-centralisation and immutability** offer a wide variety of benefits to the ENTRUST framework, namely

(i) it provides **auditability and integrity of data transactions** for establishing trust among entities, (ii) supports the **enforcement of policies in an auditable and verifiable manner**, and (iii) assists the **certifiability and auditability** of CMDs through the storage of **Conformity Certificates (CCs)**. The initial version of the Blockchain Infrastructure has been documented in D5.1 [9], where we provided a detailed description of all the internal operations needed for maintaining an up-to-date overview of the trustworthiness level of both device- and domain-level service graph chains. Here, we expand upon these descriptions and we document the final version of all Blockchain-related components and processes.

In Chapter 2, we provide an overview of the Blockchain Infrastructure of ENTRUST, based on the **Hyperledger Fabric** technology, including a description of all architectural components participating in Blockchain-related operations. We also provide descriptions of the final versions of the three core Blockchain-related action workflows of ENTRUST, specifically, (i) the **Trust Preparedness** phase, involving the **authentication, onboarding, and enrolment of the CMD into the ENTRUST domain and Blockchain network**, which includes the establishment of the required cryptographic primitives by the CMD and registering the CMD into the Blockchain Infrastructure through the issuance of a Blockchain identity certificate. (ii) The **Trust Establishment phase**, which includes the establishment of the trustworthiness of the device, and the storage of all related data on the Blockchain, such as **Conformity Certificates (CCs)** demonstrating that the device is in a trustworthy state, application-related data, attestation data, and threat intelligence data. (iii) The **Trust Maintenance** phase, which includes **re-establishment of trust upon identification of a new threat or risk** and the update of the corresponding stored information. This process also includes *the storage of the traces collected as attestation evidence after a failed attestation on the Off-chain Storage Facility.* (iv) The **Threat Intelligence Sharing**, whose purpose is to share threat intelligence information with medical domain stakeholders or organisations in a privacy-preserving manner, in order to enable risk management in different domain environments. To this end, as will be detailed in the following, we also provide further details on the tracing capabilities of ENTRUST.

Chapter 3 is dedicated to the description of the **smart contracts** employed in the context of ENTRUST, which are essentially self-executing agreements, which are stored in the Blockchain and automatically execute and enforce the contained set of actions, when a set of predefined criteria are met. In ENTRUST, smart contracts are categorised into three types, namely (i) **Application Data smart contracts**, which are responsible for managing application-related data and network traces for the inaugural establishment

of trustworthiness in medical devices, (ii) **Attestation Data smart contracts** which manage the creation, storage, and sharing of the trust state of medical devices in the ENTRUST framework, and (iii) **Trust Policy smart contracts**, which are responsible for managing the process with which the device-level and domain-level trust assessment is performed. An important addition in the context of ENTRUST is **inheritance**, which *allows a class of smart contract to inherit properties from another class, and is employed in ENTRUST to enable the separation between device-level and domain-level trust management and enable the optimal transfer of device-level information to the domain level*. In Chapter 6 we also provide detailed microbenchmarking results on the smart contracts, where we provide insights on the performance of each phase of the execution of these smart contracts such as reading or writing actions, as well as the benefits induced by the introduction of inheritance, and we extract insights from these results.

Another core operation of ENTRUST managed via the Blockchain Infrastructure pertains to **access control**, which is responsible for the management of the permissions and entities that are allowed to access the data stored on the ledger. To this end, we introduce the **Security Context Broker (SCB)**, which is a middleware entity designed to elevate security in the Hyperledger Fabric implementation and enable a granular and context-aware approach to authorisation and data protection, which is often lacking in traditional role-based access control. To this end, in Chapter 4, we present the final versions of the two core access control management operations of ENTRUST, namely (i) **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)** for ensuring that only entities that can verifiably demonstrate the possession of the required set of attributes through a **Verifiable Presentation (VP)** are able to access a particular set of data, and (ii) **Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC)** (described in Chapter 7), which ensures that only authorised entities with the required set of attributes are able to decrypt a particular set of data, and combines the capabilities of the **Attribute Based Encryption (ABE)** and **Attribute-Based Signature (ABS)** schemes.

Finally, as aforementioned, this deliverable also provides a detailed documentation of the **tracing capabilities** of ENTRUST in Chapter 5. The role of this functionality is to collect data from CMDs that enables them to provide verifiable evidence regarding their integrity and operational behaviour, which can be used as attestation evidence by the attestation enablers of ENTRUST in order to prove the correctness of their configuration state, thus acting as a **Trust Source (TS)** for the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** of ENTRUST. Thus, here we provide details on the tracing capabilities in **High-end Devices** based on the **eBPF** technology, including monitoring of information such as system call activity, library usage, binary dependencies, but also resource usage, CPU load, and memory consumption. Regarding resource-constrained **Low-end Devices**, we rely on a lightweight tracing architecture based on collecting static evidence through **secure boot validation**, where the Tracer compares a cryptographic hash of the firmware image of the device with a reference value that is known to be correct and trustworthy. We also provide detailed evaluation results for both High-end and Low-end devices, showcasing the efficiency of the tracing capabilities of ENTRUST.

Overall, this deliverable provides a detailed documentation of both the Blockchain-related operations of ENTRUST, as well as the tracing capabilities for all types of concerned CMDs. Note that the benchmarking results provided in this deliverable consider these components in a standalone manner, and provide the basis for the final evaluation activities of ENTRUST in the context of the use cases to be performed in D6.2 [10].

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Scope and Purpose

In recent years, in organisations belonging to the healthcare domain, there is an increasing trend towards the adoption of large-scale infrastructures, consisting of a large number of interconnected **Connected Medical Devices (CMDs)** with different computational capabilities, which may be subject to different security and privacy requirements. As it was documented in D2.2 [11], this increased interconnectivity between CMDs has led to the significant expansion of the threat landscape affecting such devices, as the capability to access a medical device using a different one as an entry point may introduce additional types of vulnerabilities. In addition, the ever-evolving threat landscape necessitates the capability to detect and mitigate new threats and vulnerabilities during runtime. The core target of ENTRUST is to *enhance the capability of medical organisations to provide reliable healthcare services by ensuring that the trustworthiness level of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs), as well as the system as a whole, remains at an acceptable level.* To this end, ENTRUST introduces a holistic security solution centred around a **Trust Assessment Framework**, which is able to dynamically assess the trustworthiness level of CMDs throughout their operational lifecycle.

However, considering the fact that medical devices generate vast amounts of sensitive data during their operation, including device performance metrics and operational logs, highlights the need to introduce mechanisms for addressing the emerging needs for data provenance and data trustworthiness, and ensuring the security and integrity of such data. In order to address these needs, ENTRUST introduces the use of **Blockchain technology** for the management of medical data, as its inherent properties of **immutability** and **decentralisation** provide the capability to address critical challenges, such as **data security, traceability, compliance, interoperability, and operational efficiency.** Indeed, Blockchain-based solutions comply with the relevant data management standards, namely **ISO/IEC 27001** [4] which specifies requirements for **Information Security Management Systems (ISMS)**, and **ISO 80001** [1], which provides guidelines for risk management of IT networks incorporating medical devices. In addition, as data recorded on the Blockchain cannot be modified or deleted, this ensures the integrity of device data and the maintenance of accurate historical records, thus complying with the principles of ISO/IEC 27001 regarding security and data integrity.

Another capability offered by Blockchain technologies pertains to the comprehensive **tracking of medical devices throughout their lifecycle**, encompassing all three core operational phases of ENTRUST, namely the **Design (Manufacturing) Phase**, the **Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase**, and the **Runtime Phase**. This is aligned with standards such as **ISO 13485** [2], which specifies requirements for quality management systems where the organisation needs to demonstrate its ability to provide medical devices and related services that consistently meet customer and regulatory requirements. In this regard,

every transaction or modification involving a medical device can be logged on the Blockchain, thus providing a verifiable audit trail, enhancing transparency in the supply chain, and assisting in the detection and prevention of counterfeiting. It is also aligned with **ISO 14971** [3], which specifies the application of risk management in devices operating within the medical domain. Blockchain technologies also enable the detailed tracking of the usage history, maintenance records, and performance data of a CMD, thus ensuring accountability and facilitating efficient management, in line with **ISO/TR 20416** [5], which deals with post-market surveillance.

Considering all the above, *ENTRUST employs a Blockchain infrastructure based on the Hyperledger Fabric technology, which is responsible for various functionalities regarding data sharing and provenance/auditability functionalities*, pertaining to both trustworthiness evidence and user data that need to adhere to strict privacy requirements. In addition, the Blockchain infrastructure is intended to store and manage security policy-related data and threat intelligence reports towards achieving certifiability as one important dimension of the secure lifecycle management of CMDs. As previously outlined in D5.1 [9], the conceptual Blockchain architecture of ENTRUST can be grouped into three separate flows for enabling the secure lifecycle management of CMDs, which are (i) **Trust Preparedness**, where **the device is enrolled in the ENTRUST domain and Blockchain network**, which includes the device enrolment in ENTRUST Domain for supporting the Zero-Touch Onboarding (ZTO) and registration to the Blockchain network and is performed at the beginning of the Pre-deployment Phase of the ENTRUST framework, (ii) the **equipment of the device with the necessary crypto-primitives and the trust establishment** which includes storing the Conformity Certificates (CC), the application-related data, the attestation-related data, and trust information in the Blockchain infrastructure, (iii) the **Trust Maintenance**, which includes **re-establishment of trust upon identifying a new threat or risk**, which focuses on the device's trustworthiness re-establishment (e.g., in case of a failed attestation) leading to the definition of a security policy that is enforced, which may dictate a SW/FW Update, for which updated reference values on the device's expected configuration and behaviour need to be enforced, and (iv) the **Threat Intelligence Sharing**, whose purpose is to share threat intelligence information with medical domain stakeholders or organisations in a privacy-preserving manner, in order to enable their mitigation in their respective domain infrastructures. While these flows have been described in detail in D5.1 [9], here we provide an updated description of these flows, integrated into the final version of the ENTRUST framework.

The Blockchain capabilities of ENTRUST are supported by the use of **smart contracts**, which act as programmable scripts that automatically enforce and carry out the contract terms once specific conditions are fulfilled, and allow for automated and trust-free execution of agreements within a decentralized framework. In the context of ENTRUST, as described in Chapter 2, these are split into **Application Data** smart contracts for managing the application-related data and network traces within the ENTRUST Framework for the inaugural establishment of trustworthiness in medical devices, (ii) **Attestation Data** smart contracts which are responsible for managing the creation, storage and sharing of attestation reports for the trust state of medical devices in the ENTRUST framework and enabling the establishment of trustworthiness in CMDs, and (iii) **Trust Policy** smart contracts, which are responsible for managing the trust policies based on which both device-level and domain-level trust assessment is performed, which contain all the necessary information governing the trust assessment process such as the RTL, the list of Trust Sources, and the history of the calculated ATL values. A significant addition in the context of ENTRUST is the consideration of **inheritance**, which in general *allows a class of smart contract to inherit properties from another class*. This is well-suited to the device- and domain-level consideration of ENTRUST, as *inheritance is employed in order to enable the separation between device-level and domain-level trust management and enable the optimal transfer of device-level information to the domain level*. While the initial version of these smart contracts were presented in D5.1 [9], in Chapter 3 we provide a complete description of the final version of all smart contracts of ENTRUST, and in Chapter 6 we provide detailed evaluations of each step in the enforcement of these smart contracts.

Another core operation of the Blockchain Infrastructure pertains to the management of **access control**. Specifically, in order to address the shortcomings of traditional role-based access control systems with regards to flexibility and granularity, ENTRUST offers two attribute-based schemes, which are supported by the Blockchain Infrastructure and mediated by the **Security Context Broker (SCB)**, which is designed in order to provide the required security and trustworthiness guarantees in Blockchain-related operations implemented with Hyperledger Fabric. These schemes, which are analysed in Chapter 4, are **Attribute- Based Access Control (ABAC)** for enabling granular access control to data stored on the Blockchain through the construction of a **Verifiable Presentation (VP)** containing only the required attributes in order to obtain access to a specific set of data, and **Attribute-Based SignCryption (ABSC)**, which provides sophisticated data encryption, decryption, and signing, in a manner that enables only entities with the required attributes to decrypt and access the encrypted set of data.

As detailed in the architectural flow of ENTRUST in D2.2 [11], in case of a failed attestation, the SCB is also responsible for receiving the raw trace data collected as attestation evidence by the device Tracer and storing it at the **Off-Chain Storage Facility**, along with a corresponding **location pointer** on the attestation report on the ledger. In this regard, in Chapter 5, we provide details on the tracing capabilities of ENTRUST, which can be used in order to collect data that enables devices to provide verifiable evidence on their integrity and operational behaviour. Specifically, we focus on both (i) **High-end CMDs**, where we leverage **eBPF-based tracing mechanisms**, which enable fine-grained runtime introspection at a system level and capture detailed execution properties, and (ii) **Low-end CMDs**, where tracing is based on **secure boot** validation and the Tracer compares a cryptographic hash of the firmware image at boot time with a reference value that is known to be correct. Evaluation results are also provided, measuring the overhead induced by the Tracer and verifying that it does not impede the normal operation of the CMDs.

Overall, this deliverable aims to comprehensively present the developed mechanisms for continuous authorization, trust management, CMD monitoring, and trust evidence collection within the ENTRUST framework. The primary goal is to provide stakeholders with detailed insights into the technologies and methodologies integrated into the ENTRUST blockchain infrastructure, ensuring robust security and operational assurance for CMDs throughout their lifecycle. The deliverable outlines the enhancements made since the previous deliverables, highlighting advancements in blockchain architecture, smart contract refinement, access control mechanisms, and device-specific monitoring techniques. Note that, while the benchmarking results presented in this deliverable were performed in a standalone manner, they provide the basis for the final evaluations to be performed in the context of the use cases of ENTRUST.

1.2 Relation to Other WPs and Deliverables

Figure 1.1 depicts the relationship of this deliverable with other Work Packages (WPs), as well as other tasks in the same WP(5). As aforementioned, the main purpose of this deliverable is to provide information on the design and implementation of the Blockchain Infrastructure of ENTRUST, building upon the technical and architectural groundwork laid by D5.1 [9] for Blockchain-based lifecycle management, defining the data workflows, access control schemes, and tracing mechanisms that are further refined and operationalized in this deliverable. Thus, D5.2 integrates the outcomes of these preceding works to provide a cohesive and operational framework for CMD lifecycle management. In addition, it builds upon the initial version of the tracing capabilities of ENTRUST laid out in D5.1, and provides the final version of these functionalities, as well as detailed benchmarking results.

D5.2 also leverages the advanced crypto schemes presented in D4.2 [8] and [13], namely the ABAC and ABSC schemes, and positions them within the overall Blockchain Infrastructure in order to integrate the attribute-based capabilities of ENTRUST into the overall action workflow. The tracing capabilities

presented in this deliverable also enable the collection of the required attestation evidence for the operation of the attestation enablers of ENTRUST, which act as Trust Sources (TSs) for the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) of ENTRUST, thus constituting an integral part of the overall trust assessment process of ENTRUST. All technical components have been verified to be ready for integration with all use case infrastructures, thus the evaluation of the components designed and developed as part of WP3 will be performed in the context of WP6, and their final evaluation in the context of all use case demonstrators will be documented in D6.2 [10].

Figure 1.1: Relations of D5.2 with other WPs and deliverables.

1.3 Deliverable Structure

This deliverable is structured as follows:

Chapter 2 provides a concise summary of the policy-compliant Blockchain infrastructure, outlining the architecture, workflows, and critical components.

Chapter 3 describes the finalized smart contracts, detailing their implementation and the specific data structures employed.

Chapter 4 explores the Security Context Broker (SCB), ABAC, and ABSC mechanisms within the ENTRUST Blockchain environment, emphasizing their roles in access control and data security.

Chapter 5 details monitoring techniques for CMDs, distinguishing between high-end device monitoring utilizing OP-TEE and eBPF, and low-end device monitoring emphasizing resource-constrained environments.

Chapter 6 presents the results of comprehensive benchmarking evaluations, assessing the performance of smart contract operations under various conditions.

Chapter 7 provides a detailed documentation of the Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC) scheme of ENTRUST, including detailed benchmarking results considering various evaluation scenarios.

Chapter 8 concludes the deliverable.

Chapter 2

Summary of Policy-Compliant Blockchain Infrastructure

2.1 The ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure

The ENTRUST project delivers a secure and privacy-centric framework for managing the complete life-cycle of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs). This encompasses aspects ranging from seamless auto-mated onboarding (zero-touch) to the auditable and secure management of all trust-related evidence and data: From the storage and certification of the trust state of devices (through the Conformity Certificates), based on the monitored trustworthiness evidence, to the enforcement of all trust-related policies as part of the continuous trust assessment process. Central to realizing this vision is the tailored Blockchain Infrastructure, based on Hyperledger Fabric, that underpins secure data sharing, ensures provenance, and enables comprehensive auditability. This is achieved through the enrichment of internal operations, such as **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)** and **Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC)**, which are responsible for data management operations involving interactions with the ledger in a secure and verifiable manner.

This Blockchain Infrastructure is designed to handle verifiable evidence of trustworthiness and support certification activities by enabling the continuous auditing of the Actual Trust Level of the target device through the secure management of Conformity Certificates. Furthermore, it provides robust mechanisms for managing security policies through the execution of **smart contracts**, in order to ensure the secure and auditable execution of all actions pertaining to the handling of attestation- and application-related data, as well as the sharing of threat intelligence data. With regards to the latter, *ENTRUST offers the capability to share threat intelligence data* through a **Hygiene Marketplace** leveraging the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, which enables healthcare operators to obtain information about risks and vulnerabilities identified by ENTRUST. This data is encoded using **STIX**, which is a template format which enables abstracting threat information, so that the threat intelligence information can be **shared externally to third parties or stakeholders without containing any identifiable information** (e.g., the hospital or healthcare delivery organisation where the threat was detected). It is important to note that this information is different to the one handled by the Threat Modelling component of ENTRUST, which is based on the raw evidence that led to the failed attestation of a device or a change in its trust level. This information is intended for **internal use**, in order to enable the Risk Assessment component to update the Required Trust Level (RTL) of the CMD, and by extension enables an update of the Trust Model.

The architecture of ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, as outlined in the previous deliverable D5.1, adopts a hybrid model that integrates both (i) **permissioned Blockchain networks**, which are responsible for storing sensitive trust-related information for CMDs such as **Trust Policies** per device and

attestation-related data, and (ii) **public Blockchain networks**, whose focus is the provision of auditability of the trustworthiness state of the CMD. This is achieved through the use of **Conformity Certificates (CCs)**, which are described in detail in D4.3 [13]. The public ledger is also responsible for handling the device-specific **Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD)** files and domain-specific **extended MUD** files, depicting the correct and expected behaviours of the CMD, and the process of equipping devices with the appropriate primitives via the extended EAP protocol is detailed in D3.3 [12]. This architectural choice achieves two key goals: it guarantees high-security access to sensitive medical device data for authenticated and authorized users, and it enables open access to non-sensitive data, such as Conformity Certificates and STIX-encoded cybersecurity threat intelligence, for broader transparency.

Compounding all the above, in order to address varying privacy needs, the Blockchain Infrastructure introduces three specialized data channels. (i) The first is a **private channel reserved for the execution of data sharing agreements** pertaining to trust related information, which should only be shared with the intended users and stakeholders. This includes Trust Policies (comprising Trust Models and the RTL of the CMD), as well as the management of trustworthiness evidence, which may include not only attestation evidence, but also events identified by the AI-based Anomaly Detection component. However, as such a setup may lead to profiling attacks, we have also created a **trust exposure layer** which enables obfuscating the trust-related information shared to external entities. (ii) The second is a **public channel that hosts openly shareable artifacts** like Conformity Certificates and device-specific electronic Manufacturer Usage Descriptions (eMUDs), including associated threats and vulnerabilities specific to each domain. These also include the necessary information for establishing the necessary **key restriction usage policies**, which allow for bootstrapping trust in CMDs. (iii) The third, known as the **Hygiene Marketplace channel**, is also public and facilitates the exchange and storage of STIX-formatted threat intelligence across the medical ecosystem, as aforementioned.

Compounding all the above, the Blockchain Infrastructure provides significant benefits to ENTRUST, since it not only enhances the **traceability** and **verifiability** of CMD operations, but it also provides **scalability** capabilities to the ENTRUST framework, as it supports the deployment of multiple nodes running chaincode to enable seamless on-chain operations across all channels. Thus, scalability is achieved thanks to the design choice of ENTRUST to converge the use of on- and off-chain technologies for the better management of the data lifecycle. Given the volume of raw data typically involved, ENTRUST also provides an **Off-chain Storage Facility**, which enables the storage of large volumes of encrypted data, such as raw traces collected as evidence during the execution of an attestation process, as they would be too large to store in the ledger. Towards maintaining data confidentiality and integrity, a decentralized Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC) scheme has been developed for encrypting this data before it is sent to be stored off-chain, which ensures that only duly authorized parties can access and decrypt sensitive off-chain data. This data is linked with the corresponding Trustworthiness Claims on the ledger through a location pointer, denoting the location of the data on the Off-chain Storage. Another core innovation of ENTRUST is the implementation of a **dual-layer access control system**. Specifically, at the first layer, this process leverages the **Membership Service Provider (MSP)** of the Hyperledger Fabric technology in order to ensure that a CMD has the permission to access the Blockchain Infrastructure. At the second layer, an **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)** scheme determines the level data access, as it only enables stakeholders with the appropriate permissions to access a particular set of data. Thus, this approach is able to provide a **high level of granularity to the access control process**, as it can ensure that only parties with the appropriate roles (e.g., doctors) can access specific data.

The core component responsible for orchestrating the provision of all aforementioned functionalities is the **Security Context Broker (SCB)**, which acts as a mediator between the Blockchain Infrastructure and external stakeholders. The SCB handles requests involving Blockchain Nodes, Off-chain storage facility and access control services, thereby centralizing the interaction flow and minimizing the potential attack surface. By routing all Blockchain interactions through the SCB, ENTRUST enhances governance

and oversight of data access and communication within the broader medical device ecosystem. Note that, while the notion of an SCB may seem contradicting to the decentralised nature of the Blockchain per se as it anchors the transactions to a centralised system, it is a design choice of ENTRUST that *achieves the significant reduction of the attack surface*. This means that, as a basic dimension of the ENTRUST Blockchain is on- and off-chain data management, if users were able to directly access the Blockchain, the system would be more vulnerable to malicious parties. *Thus, considering the sensitivity and importance of medical data, we opted to rescind the decentralised nature of the Blockchain to some degree, in order to reap the benefits of managing such actions through a centralised entity.*

In Section 2.2, we provide a detailed breakdown of all four core action workflows of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure. These are as follows: (i) **Trust Preparedness**, which includes all the actions that need to be taken to prepare a device for enabling it to establish its trust level. This includes the **authentication, onboarding, and enrolment of the CMD into the ENTRUST domain and Blockchain network**, as well as registering the CMD into the Blockchain Infrastructure through the issuance of a Blockchain identity certificate. (ii) **Trust and Establishment**, which includes the establishment of the trustworthiness of the device based on the crypto primitives it has been issued, and the storage of all related data on the Blockchain, such as Conformity Certificates (CCs) demonstrating that the device is in a trustworthy state, application-related data, attestation data, and threat intelligence data and (iii) **Trust Maintenance**, which entails the re-establishment of trust upon identification of a new threat or risk and the update of the corresponding stored information. This process also includes *the storage of the traces collected as attestation evidence after a failed attestation on the Off-chain Storage Facility*. (iv) **Threat Intelligence Sharing**, which includes the storage of threat intelligence data on the public ledger, to make it accessible to external stakeholders.

2.2 Workflows of ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure

The architecture of the final release of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure (see Figure 2.1) is structured around three dedicated operational flows, each designed to support the secure end-to-end lifecycle of CMDs, including the creation and maintenance of trusted CMD domains. These flows correspond to key lifecycle stages that guarantee the security of medical devices, commencing from the initial bootstrap process, where the device is securely integrated into a domain and provisioned with essential cryptographic assets, to its active runtime phase, and finally to its response mechanisms for incidents that may require a re-establishment of its trust level.

Figure 2.1: Architecture of the final release of ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure

In the following sections, we provide a step-by-step overview of the four core architectural flows defined within the ENTRUST Blockchain.

2.2.1 Trust Preparedness

The purpose of the **Trust Preparedness** flow is to enrol the CMD into the target medical domain, enable it to interact with the Blockchain Infrastructure for the secure and privacy-preserving data management, and create the required cryptographic material for enabling it to perform trust establishment during runtime. It is essentially the preparatory phase including the authentication, onboarding and enrolment of device in the ENTRUST domain and Blockchain network, and is referred to in D5.1 [9] as “Flow1: Preparing the Device for Trustworthiness Establishment”. This phase encapsulates how a device can present proof of ownership of the required attributes to the Domain Manager, prior to being enrolled into a medical service graph chain.

1. The High-end CMD communicates with the Privacy CA so that it can be authenticated and get issued its **Verifiable Credentials (VCs)**. These will comprise the attributes that will later be used in order to prove to the Domain Manager that the device has the required features in order to be onboarded to the medical domain.
2. Recall that the CMD possesses a Root ID Key. When the CMD communicates with the Privacy CA, it sends a token signed with the Root ID Key. Before authenticating and sending the VCs, this token is sent to the AAA Server (based on the extended EAP protocol, as outlined in D3.3 [12]), who is able to verify the validity of the signature by requesting the public part of the device’s Root ID Key by the Manufacturer, and identify the type of device performing the request.

3. The Manufacturer, after the signature is authenticated, sends the MUD URL of the device to the Privacy CA.
4. Based on the attributes contained in the MUD profile (e.g., vendor type, type of hardware) which is retrieved based on the location pointed by the MUD URL, the Privacy CA issues the VCs, and sends them back to the CMD. *An example structure of an MUD profile in ENTRUST is provided in the Appendix, Listing 1.*
5. Upon reception of the VCs, the CMD sends an enrolment request to the **Domain Manager (DM)** containing the **Domain ID** corresponding to the domain that the CMD wishes to be enrolled into, as well as the VC issued by the Privacy CA.
6. The DM, after receiving the request, authenticates the device by verifying its VCs, and retrieves the Device ID. Then, with the Device ID, it triggers the **Risk Assessment** process. This process leads to updating the **extended Manufacturer Usage Description (eMUD)** profile of the device with any identified threats, including domain-specific threats considering the topology of the domain. This will also lead to an update in the **Required Trust Level (RTL)** of the device, as well as the **Trust Models** that will be used to guide the trust assessment process during runtime.
7. In the meantime, the DM, knowing which are the required attributes in order to enrol the device into the specific domain, using the ABSC scheme of ENTRUST, encrypts the **Domain Key** under the necessary attributes that the device needs to exhibit. The encrypted key is then sent to the High-end CMD.
8. If the CMD possesses the necessary attributes, it is able to create the **decryption key** corresponding to the Domain Key, and responds to the DM with a signed acknowledgement. Based on this response, the DM knows that the CMD possesses the required attributes, and has correctly received the Domain Key.
9. Afterwards, the JOIN phase of the onboarding protocol is initiated (D4.2 [8]) in tandem with the DM, in order to generate the **Attestation Key (AK)** of the CMD.
10. Subsequently, the device is registered to the private channel of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, through the creation of its **Blockchain identity certificate** issued by the **Blockchain CA** through the **Membership Service Provider (MSP)**. This certificate is linked to the device's VCs and enables the secure access control of the device in the Blockchain.
11. After the generation of the required cryptographic material and prior to being able to proceed to the runtime Trust Assessment phase, two additional actions need to be taken: (i) Through the Blockchain Infrastructure, as the last step of the onboarding phase, the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** pushes to the ledger the Trust Policy containing the RTL of the device and the **Trust Model (TM)** of the particular domain. The Trust Policy dictates the type of evidence that needs to be collected for assessing the trustworthiness level of the device, and what are the trust relationships on which trust assessment needs to be performed. (ii) The CMD retrieves the credential templates based on which it can create the **Verifiable Presentation (VP)** of a **Conformity Certificate (CC)** during runtime, so that it can be pushed to the ledger.

2.2.2 Trust Establishment

During the **Trust Establishment** phase, the security/trust characterisation of the target device is conducted, based on the real-time monitored evidence, which are also stored in the Blockchain Infrastructure (for auditability in case of a failed attestation). This phase is referred to in D5.1 [9] as "Flow2: Establishing Device Trustworthiness" and encompasses the runtime trust assessment of all domain-specific

CMDs based, as aforementioned, on the real-time monitoring of trustworthiness evidence, stemming from the ENTRUST TCB, and/or the AI-based Anomaly Detection component. This (application-related and attestation-related) evidence is also stored on the Blockchain, and is also leveraged for the construction and management of Conformity Certificates (CCs), capturing any changes in the trust level of a CMD. Specifically, this process consists of the following steps:

- Having been successfully onboarded into the target domain, the CMD possesses all necessary primitives to be able to provide the required set of evidence to the TAF in the context of the trust assessment process, as well as the **Trust Model** dictated by the **Trust Source Manager (TSM)** of the TAF in order to be able to initiate and orchestrate the trustworthiness evidence collection process (as detailed in D3.2 [7]).
- In order to establish its trustworthiness during runtime, either **upon request** or **periodically**, the TAF retrieves the required trustworthiness evidence for performing the trust assessment process on the CMD. Based on this evidence, it calculates the **Actual Trustworthiness Level (ATL)** of the device, and it creates a domain-level trust appraisal by encoding it to the structure of the **Trust-worthiness Report** (see Appendix, Listing 2). This is then pushed to the ledger via the **Security Context Broker (SCB)**.
- For each CMD, each device-level trust appraisal is stored in a separate smart contract. In addition, a **domain-level trust appraisal** is also stored on the ledger, where the pointers to the latest device-level trust appraisals are pushed. Specifically, the domain-level trust appraisal is appended to the existing domain-level smart contract.
- In the meantime, in case of a failed attestation, the data collected via the device Tracer as attestation evidence needs to be stored through the Blockchain Infrastructure for auditability purposes, after being encrypted using the **Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC)** process of ENTRUST. This process is described in detail in Chapters 4 and 7, and is differentiated depending on the type of device and attributes that need to be possessed:
 - In case of a **High-end CMD**, if the device possesses the attributes based on which the ABSC process needs to be performed, it generates the required **Encryption Keys** (for each attribute) and the **Signing Key** and performs the signcryption locally. Afterwards, it sends the encrypted data to the SCB.
 - Conversely, a High-end CMD may need to perform the ABSC process **based on a set of attributes which it not possess**, but need to be demonstrated by a device in order to decrypt the data. In this case, the CMD sends the data encrypted with the **Domain Key** to the SCB, which then decrypts the data and afterwards creates the required cryptographic material and performs the ABSC process as described above.
 - In the case of a **Low-end CMD** which does not possess the required computational capabilities to perform the ABSC process, it delegates the integrity and confidentiality protection to the SCB, which then performs the ABSC process as described above.
- After the ABSC process is complete, the SCB forwards the data so that it can be stored on the **Off-chain Storage Facility**. Afterwards, the pointer to the stored data is pushed to the corresponding Trustworthiness Report on the ledger by the SCB, in order to link to their location in the Off-chain Storage.
- An additional flavour of the runtime trust assessment process is the possibility of **auditability**. This means that, upon request or based on the predefined Trust Policy, an entity may request access to a **Conformity Certificate (CC)** which conveys, in a verifiable manner, the current trustworthiness

state of a device or domain. As described in D4.3 [13], CCs in ENTRUST are aligned with the notion of **selective disclosure**, meaning that it is possible to only disclose specific attributes of its trust state. Thus, leveraging the ENTRUST TCB and crypto agility layer, a High-end CMD is able to create a VP of the CC containing only those attributes, which will be published on the ledger. Conversely, in case of a change in the trust state of the device, the TAF with the support of the DM is responsible for revoking the public CCs, as described in D4.3.

2.2.3 Trust Maintenance

The **Trust Maintenance** flow is focused on the re-establishment of trust upon identification of a new threat or risk, as well as the update of the corresponding stored information. This is referred to in D5.1 [9] as “Flow3: Re-establishing Device Trustworthiness” and includes the definition of a security policy that is subsequently enforced, involving actions like software or firmware updates. This process consists of the following steps:

- In case of a failed attestation action, the device traces collected as attestation evidence are sent to the **AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine** for further evaluation, including attack emulation in order to identify the concrete attack execution path and identify the cause of the failed attestation, as described in D3.3 [12].
- The output of this process is then sent to the **Threat Modelling** component, where a twofold process takes place. First, it is leveraged for the possible compilation of additional attack paths, enhancing the knowledge of the **Large Language Model (LLM)**-based threat profiling engine. Secondly, it is also forwarded to the **Software/Firmware Verification** component, which is able to map these newly identified anomalies into a concrete set of fuzzing test seeds, that can further extend the coverage of the fuzzing process against the target software. Any concrete attack execution paths identified are then forwarded to the **Risk Assessment (RA)** engine for further processing and refining the **Required Trust Level (RTL)** of the device and the domain.
- Based on the output of this process, the **Security Administrator** creates an updated software binary with the necessary patches in order to address the identified vulnerabilities.
- The updated binary is forwarded to the **Software Service Provider** so that it can be signed, and then uploaded to the Blockchain Infrastructure, so that the update process can be initiated.
- A notification of an available update is then pushed to the intended devices through the **Subfleet Manager** on the Digital Twin, which acts as an intermediary between the Secure Software Update component and the CMDs, and is responsible for coordinating and managing the update process across all intended devices, ensuring that each device receives the appropriate updates securely and efficiently.
- Following the identification of a new risk, the MUD profile of the CMD needs to be updated with the newly identified threats and vulnerabilities, as well as the new **policy hash** representing the expected configuration of the device. Then, the DM receives the updated profile so that it is able to provide the updated **key restriction usage policy** to the CMD through the **Verifiable Policy Enforcer (VPE)**, so that it is able to attest and verify the correctness of the device state, based on its newly updated configuration stack.

2.2.4 Threat Intelligence Sharing

The purpose of the **Threat Intelligence Sharing** flow is to make information regarding newly identified threats or vulnerabilities accessible in a privacy-preserving manner, so that other stakeholders or medical domain organisations are able to obtain information about them and appropriately manage them in their respective domains. This process consists of the following steps:

1. As a result of the **Trust Maintenance** workflow detailed in Section 2.2.3, the **Risk Assessment (RA) Engine** obtains the evidence extracted from the failed attestation process, including the attack execution paths identified by the **Software Verification component**, the Risk Indicators provided by the **AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine**, and the attack scenarios by the **Threat Modelling** component.
2. Based on the available threat information, and considering the **asset topology** of the domain, the RA Engine performs risk re-evaluation, resulting not only the **risk quantification** pertaining to a CMD where a risk level is computed for each identified threat, but also possible **security controls** that may be enforced in order to mitigate a specific risk.
3. The risk indices resulting from the risk assessment process are encoded in the **STIX format**, which is a standardised language for exchanging cyber threat intelligence. The key aspect of this representation is the ability to *abstract any sensitive information regarding the threat, such as the organisation where it was identified*, thus enabling the exchange of cyber threat intelligence in a privacy-preserving manner.
4. After being STIX-encoded, the threat intelligence data is pushed to the **Hygiene Marketplace**, which is a public channel on the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure that allows external users or stakeholders in the medical domain to access this data and mitigate the identified risks in their own domain (as aforementioned, without learning any personally identifiable information about those threats).

2.3 Updates to the Blockchain Infrastructure in the Final Release

Compounding all the above, Table 2.1 lists the updates performed in the final version of the Blockchain Infrastructure, compared to the first release which was documented in D5.1 [9], as well as the Tracing capabilities of ENTRUST. These are presented throughout this deliverable, and are included in the final release of the ENTRUST Blockchain.

Table 2.1: Updates to the Blockchain Infrastructure in the Final Release

Update	Description
Blockchain Architecture	We have finalised and clarified all flows involving the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, as described throughout this Chapter, including their positioning within the overall ENTRUST framework. These especially pertain to actions related to device onboarding, enforcement of Trust Models, and handling of MUDs and eMUDs.
Smart Contracts	As detailed in Chapter 3, we have defined and implemented the final versions of all trust-related smart contracts. In addition, we have performed detailed benchmarking of the execution of the smart contracts, focusing on a wide variety of internal operations, reading and writing operations, concurrent operations, batching, and the effect of ledger height on the efficiency of the operations.

<p>Building Blocks</p>	<p>We have constructed and finalised the implementation of all Blockchain-related components and building blocks. Note that the integration of the Blockchain Infrastructure, as well as all building blocks, will be evaluated in D6.2 [10] in the context of all the use cases, and End-to-End (E2E) evaluations will be performed.</p>
<p>Runtime Tracer</p>	<p>We have finalised the design and implementation of the eBPF-based tracing capabilities in both High-end and Low-end devices. In the case of the High-end devices, we have performed benchmarking tests in order to evaluate the overhead induced by the Tracer, and we concluded that it does not impact the normal operation of the CMD. In the case of Low-end devices, we have investigated the capability to integrate different types of metrics, such as power consumption.</p>

Chapter 3

Final Smart Contract Definition and Implementation

3.1 Smart contracts in ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure

Smart contracts comprise a paradigm in agreement execution, operating as self-executing contracts with the terms of the agreement directly written into lines of code. They are stored on a Blockchain network and they automatically execute and enforce the agreed-upon conditions when predefined criteria are met, eliminating the need for traditional intermediaries. This inherent decentralization of smart contracts fosters trust, as all participants can verify the code and execution of a contract on the ledger. The immutability of smart contracts ensures that once deployed, they cannot be altered, providing tamper-proof assurance.

As such, the design and implementation of smart contracts in the final release of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure enables the secure and auditable performance of data transactions, towards handling trust-worthiness evidence data such as attestation evidence, trust policies and application data for the safe-guarded operation of connected medical devices in the healthcare domain.

An important feature of the smart contracts in ENTRUST Blockchain is **inheritance**, the well-known mechanism that allows a class (e.g., child) to inherit properties and behaviors from another class (e.g., parent), as a fundamental concept in object-oriented programming (OOP) that facilitates code reuse and introduces relationships between classes. *Inheritance in ENTRUST is employed to enable the separation between device-level and domain-level trust management and allow the optimal transfer of device-level information to domain-level.* In this context, inheritance provides the advantage of performing fewer data transactions to update domain-level based on device-level data. In the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, two types of inheritance are supported through the corresponding smart contracts: (a) **Single Inheritance**, with which the Domain-level CC (child) inherits data from the Device-level CC (parent), and (b) **Multiple Inheritance**, with which the Domain-level Trust Policy (child) inherits the Device-level Trust Policy from all the medical devices (parents) enrolled in the specific domain.

3.2 Smart Contract Functions for Data Management

This section outlines the different types of smart contracts employed in ENTRUST, in order to facilitate the execution of operations within the ENTRUST Blockchain Framework in a secure and transparent manner. To this end 3.1 details the **smart contract functions** employed, as well as the implementation status,

i.e., specifying if they were released in the first or the second version of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure. Note that the functions listed as being completed in the 1st release have been both implemented and integrated, while the ones listed for the 2nd release have been implemented in a standalone manner and will be integrated in the final release of the ENTRUST framework.

In general, smart contract functions, can be categorised into two types:

- **Exported (E):** Functions responsible for calling and implementing smart contracts of the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure, typically starting with an uppercase letter.
- **Unexported (U):** Sub-functions and variables that necessitate a smart contract to operate as designed, usually starting with a lowercase letter.

Table 3.1: Smart contract functions of ENTRUST

Type	Smart Contract Function	Description	Release	Accountable
E	AuthenticateUserBCCert()	Authenticates a user's Blockchain certificate before allowing access to sensitive functions and Blockchain channels. Utilizes MSP-based Fabric authentication and is the first check in ENTRUST's two-layered access control.	1.0	SCB
E	PostApplicationData()	Creates a smart contract for initiating and collecting application data, then stores it via storeApplicationData().	2.0	SCB
E	PostTrustworthinessEvidence()	Creates a smart contract to collect trustworthiness evidence according to the Trust Policy. Uses storeAttestationData() to store it. TAF is notified when new evidence is stored.	1.0	SCB
U	storeApplicationData()	Checks access with getAccess(), and if authorized, stores application-related data via storeOffChainDataAndDBPointer(). Uses Off-Chain Storage when needed.	2.0	Fabric Ledger + Off-Chain Data Storage
U	storeAttestationData()	Similar to storeApplicationData() but for attestation reports.	1.0	Fabric Ledger + Off-Chain Data Storage
U	getAccess()	Performs access control based on ABAC, VPs, and ABE. Called on every transaction.	1.0 (ABAC, assuming a valid VP signed with ABSC) and 2.0 (ABSC integration)	SCB, ABAC, ABE
U	storeOffChainDataAndDBPointer()	Securely stores data off-chain and writes pointer to the ledger. Uses ABE for encryption.	2.0	Fabric Ledger + Off-Chain Data Storage + ABE
E	QueryApplicationData()	Retrieves application data after authorization via getAccess(). Invoked by AI or auditors.	1.0	Fabric Ledger + Off-Chain Data Storage + SCB

E	QueryAttestationData()	Retrieves attestation data after authorization via <code>getAccess()</code> . Invoked by TAF or auditors.	1.0	Fabric Ledger + Off-Chain Data Storage + SCB
E	PostTrustPolicy()	Creates trust policy via <code>getAccess()</code> and <code>createTrustPolicy()</code> .	1.0	SCB
U	createTrustTemplate()	Creates the trust template which triggers trust model creation.	1.0	Fabric Ledger + SCB
U	createTrustPolicy()	Defines the parameters governing the trust process, including ATL, RTL, and periodicity.	1.0	Fabric Ledger + SCB
E	QueryTrustLevel()	Interface to retrieve device or domain trust level for authorized entities.	2.0	Fabric Ledger + SCB
U	applySecurityPolicy()	Enforces mitigation policies resulting from risk assessment.	2.0	SCB + Risk Assessment + Mitigation Policy Enforcement
E	PostThreatIntelligenceData()	Collects and stores harmonized threat intel in STIX format in the Hygiene Marketplace. Uses <code>getAccess()</code> .	2.0	Fabric Ledger + SCB
E	QueryThreatIntelligenceData()	Retrieves threat intelligence data from the ledger. Uses <code>getAccess()</code> .	2.0	Fabric Ledger + SCB
U	storeCC()	Stores Device/Domain-level CC and accompanying challenge on the ledger.	2.0	Fabric Ledger
E	QueryCC()	Retrieves stored CC per device or domain.	2.0	Fabric Ledger

3.3 Final version of smart contracts

The final data model definition of the different smart contracts in the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure that facilitate data transactions to ensure the establishment of trustworthiness in the medical devices within the ENTRUST Framework are presented below.

Application Data Smart Contracts

These contracts are implemented to manage the application-related data and network traces within the ENTRUST Framework (Table 3.2) for the inaugural establishment of trustworthiness in medical devices, as described in the second workflow in Section 2.2.2.

Table 3.2: Application-data Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
reportID	string	json:"reportID"	A string identifier used as a unique key to identify application-specific data.
deviceID	string	json:"deviceID"	A string identification used to identify the device derived from application related data.
createdAt	string	json:"createdAt"	The application report comprises a string identification that represents the date of its creation (e.g., timestamp).
listOfAttributes	[] string	json:"listOfAttributes"	This field refers to the list of attributes that a device or party must possess, to be able to read this particular application report.
Result	[] string	json:"result"	Includes the indications of each device depending on what kind of device is mentioned each time, for example a device measures temperature the result could be "temperature: 68°F".
Signature	string	json:"signature"	Signature of the medical device.
DBpointer	string	json:"DBpointer"	Pointer to off-chain.

Attestation Data Smart Contracts

These contracts are implemented to manage the creation, storage and sharing of attestation reports for the trust state of medical devices in the ENTRUST Framework (Table 3.3), enabling the establishment of trustworthiness in CMDs as dictated in the second workflow in section 2.2.2.

Table 3.3: Attestation-report Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
reportID	string	json:"reportID"	A string identifier that serves as a unique key for representing a given attestation report.
deviceID	string	json:"deviceID"	A string identifier pointing to the specific device the attestation report is referring to.
createdAt	string	json:"createdAt"	The string identifier stores the creation date (e.g., timestamp). This feature allows for intricate searches on the ledger that rely on the date of creation.
listOfAttributes	[] string	json:"listOfAttributes"	This field specifies the list of access attributes that a given device or entity must possess to access and edit this specific data structure from the DLT.
Result	bool	json:"result"	Represents the outcome of the attestation, which might be either "pass" or "fail" based on the success or failure of the attestation.
AttestationPublic Keys	Attestation PKI	json:"attestation PublicKeys"	An AttestationPKI struct, which contains the DAA credentials of device and enclaves that are responsible to create the attestation.
Signature	string	json:"signature"	Signature of the medical device.
DBpointer	string	json:" DBPointer"	Pointer to off-chain. When an attestation is applied to a device, the result is a series of memory addresses that are stored in an off-chain data storage. This pointer is constructed to establish a connection with this data storage.

Trust Policies Smart Contracts

These contracts are implemented to manage the trust model based on which both device-level and domain-level trust assessment is performed. Trust policies keep all the necessary information governing the trust assessment process such as the RTL, the list of trust evidence/sources as well as the history of the ATL values for each device and subsequently each domain (Tables 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7). The device-level ATL data structure is included in the device-level Trust Policy data structure, while the domain-level ATL data structure is included in the domain-level Trust Policy data structure. The corresponding smart contracts for device-level and domain-level Trust Policy facilitate the preparation for the establishment of trustworthiness in CMDs as presented in the first workflow in section 2.2.1.

Table 3.4: Device-level ATL Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
TrustLvValue	[] string	json: "trustLvValue"	Indicates the trust opinion calculation derived by the Trust-level Expression Engine of the TAF for the target device trust model.
Signature	[] string	json: "signature"	This is the signature of TAF component.
DBpointer	[] string	json: "DBpointer"	Indicates the Off-chain Data Storage pointer of the evidence upon which the trust level is generated.

Table 3.5: Domain-level ATL Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
TrustLvValue	[] string	json: "trustLvValue"	Indicates the trust opinion calculation of the domain based on fusion of trust opinions of each one of the domain's medical devices.
Signature	[] string	json: "signature"	This is the signature of TAF component.
DBpointer	[] string	json: "DBpointer"	Indicates the Off-chain Data Storage pointers of the evidence upon which the trust level is generated for all the devices belonging to the domain.

Table 3.6: Device-level Trust Policy Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
DeviceID	string	json: "DeviceID"	This represents the medical device (e.g., CMD).
ATL	[] struct	json: "actualtrustlevel"	The Actual Trust Level (ATL) of the device that is evaluated periodically. Is derived from the computation based on the trustworthiness evidence of device to be determined if the device meets the requirements of the RTL.

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
RTL	[] integer	json: "requiredtrustlevel"	The Required Trust Level (RTL) is a baseline of the trust level that a CMD device needs to exhibit to be deemed trustworthy. This translates to an evaluation of the runtime ATL against this RTL. This is calculated as part of the Risk Assessment considering the device-specific threats and vulnerabilities from the manufacturer. Is a measure of the trustworthiness of the device before uploading the trustworthiness evidence to the Blockchain, to perform the runtime assessment.
TrustModel	[] string	json: "trustmodel"	Represents the type of data each device generates (e.g., OS, SW stack etc.) necessary for evaluating the trust level of the device.
ListOfTrust Properties	[] string	json: "listoftrust-properties"	An array of strings generated by TAF representing the trust opinion assessment (e.g., trust properties) for the specific device (e.g., integrity, confidentiality, etc.).
ListOfTrustSource	[] string	json: "listoftrustsource"	The type of evidences we need to monitor such as attestation evidence or AI-based anomaly detection evidence.
Periodicity	integer	json: "periodicity"	The frequency of retrieving the trustworthiness evidence from the device in a synchronous-based monitoring.
eMUDPointer	[] string	json: "eMUDPointer"	A string identifier pointing to the manufacturer's Device-level eMUD.
CCPointer	[] string	json: "CCPointer"	A string identifier pointing to the list of Device-level CCs generated by the specific policy.
ListOfAccess Attributes	[] string	json: "accessAttributes"	Set of access properties.
Signature	[] string	json: "signature"	This is the signature of Domain Manager.

Table 3.7: Domain-level Trust Policy Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
DomainID	string	json: "DomainID"	This represents the Domain.
ListOfDeviceID	[] string	json: "ListOfDeviceID"	An array of strings that is calculated automatically based on the Device IDs as inherited by the Device-level Trust Policy of the devices enrolled in the domain.
ATL	[] struct	json: "actualtrustlevel"	The Actual Trust Level (ATL) is derived from the computation based on the trustworthiness evidence of services to be determined if the container of services meets the requirements of the RTL.
RTL	[] struct	json: "requiredtrustlevel"	The Required Trust Level (RTL) is a baseline of the trust level that a CMD domain needs to exhibit to be deemed trustworthy. This translates to an evaluation of the runtime ATL against this RTL. This is calculated as part of the Risk Assessment considering the device-specific threats and vulnerabilities from the manufacturer, inherited by the Device-level Trust Policy, and enriched with additional attack vectors (e.g., threats and vulnerabilities) emerged during onboarding in the domain.
TrustModel	[] string	json: "trustmodel"	An array of strings that captures the medical devices relationships of the domain that need to be established and we need to assess the trust level. It also inherits the types of data that each device generates.
ListOfTrust Properties	[] string	json: "listoftrust-properties"	An inherited list of strings concatenated by the comprised devices of the specific domain.
ListOfTrustSource	[] string	json: "listoftrustsource"	The type of evidence we need to monitor such as attestation evidence or AI-based anomaly detection evidence.
Periodicity	integer	json: "periodicity"	Periodicity refers to the frequency at which the Domain Manager decides to request and collect trustworthiness evidence.

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
eMUDPointer	[] string	json: "eMUDPointer"	A string identifier pointing to the Domain-level eMUD.
CCPointer	[] string	json: "CCPointer"	A string identifier pointing to the list of Domain-level CCs generated by the specific policy.
ListOfAttributes	[] string	json: "listofattributes"	This field specifies the list of attributes that a given device or entity must possess to access and edit this specific data structure from the DLT.

Conformity Certificates Smart Contracts

These contracts are implemented to handle the creation and storage of Conformity Certificates per device and per domain in the ENTRUST Framework (Table 3.8) for the establishment of trustworthiness in CMDs as described in the second workflow in section 2.2.2.

Table 3.8: Device/Domain CC Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
ID	string	json: "ID"	This represents either the device or domain. (e.g., DeviceID or DomainID)
CC	string	json: "CC"	This is a W3C Verifiable Presentation based on trustworthiness certificate issued by the TAF for the list of trust properties of interest defined in associated trust policy.

Extended MUD Smart Contracts

These contracts are implemented to handle the storage in the ENTRUST Blockchain of eMUD files for all devices comprising a domain (Table 3.8), enabling the enrollment of CMDs in the ENTRUST Framework as presented in the first workflow in section 2.2.1.

Table 3.9: Domain eMUD Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
DeviceID	string	json: "DeviceID"	This represents the medical device (e.g., CMD).
DomainID	string	json: "DomainID"	This represents the Domain.
swStack	[] string	json: "swStack"	It includes the SW, FW and OS versions of the device.
sysChars	[] string	json: "sysChars"	Represents the system characteristics of the device.
cryptoCap	[] string	json: "cryptoCap"	Represents the crypto capabilities of the device.
threats	[] string	json: "threats"	List of vulnerabilities and weakness identified by the manufacturer, enriched with the potential attack vectors of the domain identified by the risk assessment.
mitigation	[] string	json: "mitigation"	List of mitigations identified by the manufacturer, enriched with the potential mitigation actions relevant the attack vectors of the domain.
policyHashes	[] string	json: "mitigation"	Reference configuration values for all the binaries comprises the SW stack based on which the key restriction usage policies (e.g., key policy hashes) are created. Based on these policies the attestation key is created during the onboarding of the specific device in the domain.

Threat Intelligence Data Smart Contracts

These contracts are implemented to handle the storage of threat intelligence data in a structured and privacy-preserving STIX format in the Hygiene Marketplace of the ENTRUST Blockchain (Table 3.10) to be available for other medical domain stakeholders as presented in the fourth workflow in 2.2.4.

Table 3.10: Threat Intelligence (STIX 2)

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
type	string	json: "type"	The value of this property MUST be campaign.
id	string	json: "id"	A name used to identify the Campaign.
spec_version	string	json: "spec_version"	A description that provides more details and context about the Campaign, potentially including its purpose and its key characteristics.
created	string	json: "created"	The string identifier stores the creation date (e.g., timestamp).
modified	string	json: "modified"	The string identifier stores the modification date (e.g., timestamp).
name	string	json: "name"	The string identifier stores the name.
description	string	json: "description"	A description that provides more details and context about the identified threat.

Chapter 4

The SCB and Access Policies in ENTRUST Blockchain

While the Hyperledger Fabric technology offers robust foundational security, in complex environments such as the ENTRUST framework, a more granular and context-aware approach for authorization and data protection is required in order to be able to fulfil the needs of the medical organisations with regards to their requirements on data access. Traditional **role-based access control (RBAC)** often falls short for modern security requirements, while static encryption lacks the flexibility needed for dynamic data sharing.

To this end, the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure introduces the **Security Context Broker (SCB)** as an innovative middleware component designed to elevate security in Hyperledger Fabric implementation. In this regard, the functionality of the SCB in the context of the ENTRUST framework is twofold: (i) it is responsible for **acting as a bridge between the Blockchain Infrastructure and external entities for the execution of on-chain transactions and attribute-based policies**, and (ii) it **orchestrates the execution of data-sharing agreements and transactions by connecting data stored on-chain and off-chain through the appropriate encrypted pointers**.

In the following, we go into further detail regarding the two aforementioned functionalities of the SCB, and its role within the overall operations of the Blockchain within the ENTRUST framework. Note that, with regards to the former, the **Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC)** scheme is a core innovation of ENTRUST, which combines **Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE)** and **Attribute-Based signature (ABS)** capabilities in order to provide confidentiality and authenticity for data in a fine-grained manner, and it allows senders to encrypt messages based on access policies defined by attributes, and simultaneously sign the message with their own attributes, ensuring both secrecy and integrity. While the ENTRUST ABSC scheme is described here at a high level, it is also described in detail in Chapter 7, where we also provide benchmarking results that demonstrate its efficiency and performance.

4.1 The SCB as a fundamental mediator in ENTRUST Blockchain

As aforementioned, the SCB provides two core functionalities, which are essential parts of the action workflow of the ENTRUST framework, as detailed in Chapter 2. Here, we expand upon these two functionalities, and we provide details on their application within ENTRUST, highlighting the role of the SCB as a fundamental mediator in the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure.

The SCB as a bridge between the Blockchain Infrastructure and external entities for the execution of on-chain transactions and attribute-based policies: This functionality is a core innovation of ENTRUST which converges the use of advanced *crypto primitives* with a *two-layer access control* methodology, leveraging the capabilities of the underlying Blockchain Infrastructure, and namely **Hyper-ledger Fabric**. In this regard, the Blockchain Infrastructure supports the execution of the ABSC scheme for sophisticated data encryption and decryption, specifically tailored for the ENTRUST Framework. In the context of ENTRUST, ABSC may be performed by **High-end CMDs** with the capability to support the underlying mathematical operations. Specifically, the High-end CMD may leverage its **Verifiable Credentials (VCs)** issued during the enrolment phase by the Privacy CA in order to manifest the type of attributes that can be exhibited by the device, in order to *encrypt a set of data under a specific set of attributes, which also need to be exhibited by the receiving entity*. In order to perform this operation, the High-end CMD is able to locally self-issue an encryption key.

In the case of **Low-end CMDs** which may not possess the required computational capabilities, the execution of the ABSC scheme may be delegated either to the SCB, or to their parent High-end Device, for *associating attribute-based policies to the application of trustworthiness-related data agreements*. However, if it does not wish to delegate this operation, it can *leverage the Domain Key which was released to the CMD upon onboarding* in order to establish a secure communication channel with the SCB, which will then encrypt the data under the required set of attributes, leveraging the same ABSC scheme. A core innovation of ENTRUST in this regard is the design and implementation of a **decentralised ABSC scheme**. Specifically, *a Verifier may request access to a set of encrypted data, if and only if it exhibits the required attributes, by dynamically creating the required decryption keys via the ENTRUST TCB*.

This process has also been implemented to work in tandem with a novel **two-layer Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)** scheme which is orchestrated and enforced with the SCB. Specifically, at the first layer, this scheme leverages the default **Membership Service Provider (MSP)** from the underlying Hyperledger Fabric Blockchain Infrastructure, which is responsible for issuing certificates per user per device. Then, ENTRUST binds this certificate to the VCs of the High-end CMD (which was already issued when it was onboarded to the domain). This allows the CMD to present a VP to the SCB, which it can forward to the MSP for verifying its correct binding to the correct Blockchain-related certificate. If successful, the SCB can ratify that the necessary attributes are present in the credential in order to verify that the entity can interact with the Blockchain. At the second level, the ABAC scheme determines the level of granularity in data access, as it determines if the attributes possessed by the device are sufficient in order to access the particular set of data.

The SCB as an orchestrator of the execution of data-sharing agreements and transactions by connecting data stored on-chain and off-chain through the appropriate encrypted pointers: Recall that the ABSC scheme is responsible for the encryption and signing of a set of data, leveraging attribute-based crypto primitives. After this is performed, the second modality of the SCB involves the execution of data-sharing agreements, which involve the storage of encrypted data on the Blockchain Infrastructure. This entails controlling which data is stored on-chain and which is stored off-chain. Consider the execution of an attestation operation, which entails the collection of device traces as attestation evidence, leveraging the attestation capabilities of ENTRUST. In this case, **the encrypted data is sent to the SCB which forwards them to be stored off-chain**, as their large volume does not enable their storage on the ledger, while **the trustworthiness claims are stored on-chain**. Then, an associated pointer to the off-chain data will be pushed as part of the on-chain trustworthiness claim.

Considering all the above, the SCB acts as a central component, enabling both advanced ABAC capabilities for authorization, and ABSC for sophisticated data encryption and decryption. The SCB efficiently collects and manages rich security attributes from diverse sources, like user identity, organizational roles,

etc. The SCB delivers high granularity towards achieving control over who can access specific information in the ENTRUST Blockchain. It provides agile policy management, allowing security policies to be defined and enforced centrally. Enhanced data security is enabled by safeguarding sensitive operation information of medical devices with a sophisticated ABSC scheme. This process guarantees that a unified security context is available for all transactions and data interactions within the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure.

Within the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, the Security Context Broker (SCB) constitutes a central and trusted facilitator for all transactions (see Figure 4.2). It acts as a secure intermediary, managing and coordinating every interaction between different parts of the Blockchain and external entities in ENTRUST Framework. Some core architectural and design details of the SCB can be summarised as follows:

- Recall that one of the two main functions of the SCB is to monitor and enforce secure data sharing processes. It is the single communication point for initiating any transaction on the ENTRUST Blockchain and **strictly controls which entities can access data within the ENTRUST Framework**. By connecting Blockchain smart contracts with external off-chain data sources, the SCB enables these contracts to utilize information not stored directly on the Blockchain.
- The SCB conveys requests from various ENTRUST entities to the Blockchain Ledgers and Off-chain Storage. A key innovation of the SCB is its **"chaincode-as-a-service"** model, which is built on a REST API framework. This allows any enrolled device to call the smart contract services as if they were local, regardless of their programming language, because the necessary code is generated dynamically. This makes it possible to access, deploy and execute chaincode instantly, even from outside the Blockchain network, while maintaining strict user authorization.
- The SCB is developed based on the **Node.js** framework and exploits its REST API interfaces to comprise a unified layer for secure transactions within the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure.
- The SCB operates on an **event-based architecture** that facilitates issues such as the secure handling of large datasets, by deciding whether to store them on-chain or off-chain, and the execution of smart contracts upon receiving respective data for storage from authorized ENTRUST entities. Furthermore, the SCB ensures auditability and compliance by logging every access request and data transaction in the Blockchain, eventually creating an transparent and immutable record of all Blockchain activities.
- To foster strict access control in the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, the SCB primarily interacts with **Blockchain Peers** and the **Membership Service Provider (MSP)** to employ ABAC using smart contracts and leveraging the verifiable credentials of ENTRUST entities. For further ensuring the security of data stored in the Off-Chain Storage, the SCB applies ABSC to securely sign and encrypt data.
- The **centralized design** of the SCB enables the **high auditability and access control** in ENTRUST Blockchain, by enforcing at the same moment the decentralized nature of the Blockchain for advanced security of data transaction in ENTRUST Framework to safeguard the trustworthy operation of connected medical devices.

4.2 Advanced ENTRUST Crypto Leveraging SCB

In this section, we provide a high-level overview of the advanced crypto offered by ENTRUST, and we detail the role of the SCB and the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure in these processes. First, we focus

on the process that entails the execution of the **Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC)** scheme so that either a Low-end or High-end CMD is able to produce an encrypted and signed set of data, as well as the access control process that enables the CMD to obtain access to the Blockchain infrastructure in order to store the encrypted data. This process is depicted in the sequence diagram of Figure 4.1 and consists of the following steps:

Figure 4.1: ABSC and Two-layer authorization with ABAC in ENTRUST BC

- In case a **High-end CMD** wishes to perform the ABSC process on a set of data, we consider two distinct scenarios: (i) The case where **the CMD possesses the set of attributes based on which the signcryption needs to be performed**, and (ii) the case where **signcryption needs to be performed using attributes that the CMD does not possess** (but need to be possessed by the entity that is going to decrypt the data). In the first case, the process is as follows (**Flow A**):

(a) The High-end CMD leverages its ENTRUST TCB in order to locally generate **Encryption**

Keys and **Signing Keys** based on the attributes with which the ABSC process needs to be performed. Note that these keys can be created under either the same or a different set of attributes.

- (b) The High-end CMD process encrypts and signs the data using the ABSC process, leveraging the generated Encryption Keys. *Note that here we do not go into further details on the specifics of the ABSC scheme, as it is described in detail in Chapter 7.*
- (c) The encrypted data is sent to the SCB so that it can be forwarded to be stored on the Blockchain Infrastructure later on in the process (after the verification of the CMD).

2. In the second case, the process is formulated as follows (**Flow B**):

- (a) The CMD sends the data, encrypted using the **Domain Key** that was released to the CMD during the domain onboarding process.
- (b) The SCB decrypts the data and generates the Encryption Keys and Signing Keys for the attributes that the ABSC process will be performed with, including the attributes not possessed by the CMD. As in the previous case, these can be created under either the same or a different set of attributes, depending on the policy.
- (c) The SCB encrypts and signs the data performed with the ABSC scheme. Note that, while in Flow A the ABSC process is performed at the side of the High-end CMD, here it is performed at the SCB.

3. In case a **Low-end CMD** is the one who wishes to perform the ABSC process, since it does not possess the required computational capabilities to perform the underlying mathematical operations, it is able to delegate the protection of the confidentiality and integrity of the data. This conceptually changes the trust model of the process, as the SCB in this case is responsible for handling the Encryption and Signing Keys, including their creation. *In this case, the process followed is identical to **Flow B** outlined above.*

4. The High-end CMD creates a **Verifiable Presentation (VP)** containing the set of attributes needed so that the device is able to obtain permission to access the Blockchain network.

5. Next, the **two-layer access control** is performed, in order to allow the access of the device to the Blockchain Infrastructure and enable the storage of the data on the Blockchain Infrastructure. The **first layer**, which aims to determine whether the CMD has the permission to access the Blockchain or not, is as follows:

- (a) The CMD sends the VP to the SCB so that it can initiate the authorisation process.
- (b) The SCB relays the VP to the **Membership Service Provider (MSP)**, so that it can check that the **Blockchain Certificate** of the device is correctly bound to that VP.
- (c) The MSP verifies the binding expression of the Blockchain certificate with VP by extracting the **binding assertion**. If successful, it relays the assertion to the SCB to notify it that the CMD is permitted to access the Blockchain.

6. The **second layer**, which aims to determine the level of access of the CMD to the Blockchain network, is as follows:

- (a) After the MSP has authorised access to the Blockchain, the SCB extracts the attributes contained in the VP and it checks them against **pre-existing policies**. Correspondingly, Low-end devices can access the Blockchain through their associated high-end devices, by offering their credentials that had been issued at their enrolment phase, as described in D4.2 [8] and D4.3 [13]. As such, when the VPs of a CMD fulfil the ABAC access policies, the SCB grants access to the CMD to enter the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure.

and maintaining system integrity through authenticated, verifiable interactions. Table 4.1 provides a detailed list of the core interfaces of the SCB. In addition, Figure 4.2 provides a mapping of the interfaces with the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, in order to better illustrate their positioning within the overall ENTRUST framework.

Table 4.1: Externally Accessible SCB Interfaces

Interface ID	Name	Description	Invocation	Notes
SCB.EX.1	Query Application Data	Allows authorized ENTRUST users or stakeholders to retrieve validated application data.	HTTPS + ABAC	Requires Verifiable Presentation.
SCB.EX.2	Query Latest Attestation Reports	Enables secure access to the latest attestation reports stored on the ledger, based on requester's access policies.	HTTPS + ABAC	Signature and attribute checks are enforced before retrieval. This service is accessed either by the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) of ENTRUST, or an external certification authority.
SCB.EX.3a	Store MUD Profiles	Manages the Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) profiles for registered CMDs with embedding the required additional information (e.g., policy hashes) during the secure onboarding of a CMD into the domain.	HTTPS	Interfaced with internal SCB device registry; used for behaviour profiling and risk checks.
SCB.EX.3b	Query MUD Profiles	Retrieves Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) profiles for registered IoT devices.	HTTPS	Interfaced with internal SCB device registry; used for behaviour profiling and risk checks.
SCB.EX.4	Query SW/FW Update	Retrieves SW/FW Update for the registered IoT devices.	HTTPS + ABAC	Interfaced with internal SCB device registry; used for SW/FW Update.

All interfaces are RESTful and implemented in **Node.js**, making use of standard JSON schemas. Before execution, the SCB validates each request using aligned **W3C Verifiable Presentations**, performing cryptographic checks and attribute evaluation based on policy rules. While these are the public-facing endpoints within ENTRUST, the SCB also includes a comprehensive set of internal, event-triggered interfaces that orchestrate the secure data flows across various components and the off-chain storage. These internal interfaces are not exposed externally and are executed automatically based on pre-defined event triggers, ensuring seamless operation across the Blockchain infrastructure without manual intervention. Together, this architecture enables the SCB to function as both a secure policy enforcer and a reliable dispatcher for inter-component logic across ENTRUST.

Chapter 5

CMD Monitoring

The *Tracer* component, as introduced in D5.1 [9], plays a pivotal role in enabling runtime attestation and trust monitoring within the ENTRUST architecture. Its core function is to collect trace data from CMDs and provide verifiable evidence regarding their integrity and operational behaviour. This evidence is fundamental to ENTRUST's trust assessment pipeline and is categorized into two principal classes: **static** and **runtime** properties. Each class serves distinct yet complementary purposes within the overall trust lifecycle. ENTRUST provides tracing capabilities that support the *continuous assessment of trust*, with adaptability to the heterogeneity of CMDs across various operational contexts. Recognizing the diversity in hardware profiles and operating environments in medical deployments, ENTRUST differentiates its approach between **high-end** and **low-end** CMD monitoring strategies.

For **high-end CMDs**, ENTRUST leverages advanced tracing mechanisms based on the *eBPF* technology. These tracers enable fine-grained runtime introspection at the system level, capturing detailed execution properties such as system call activity, library usage, and binary dependencies. Additionally, eBPF-based mechanisms monitor resource usage, including CPU load and memory consumption. Beyond runtime metrics, the Tracer also performs static validation by verifying the integrity of user-space binaries and libraries against trusted cryptographic fingerprints. This combination of dynamic and static monitoring enables high-resolution telemetry collection, suitable for in-depth anomaly detection, trust level inference, and dynamic policy enforcement.

In contrast, **low-end CMDs**, which operate under constrained computational and memory conditions, rely on a lightweight tracing architecture. Static evidence is collected through *secure boot validation*, where the Tracer computes a cryptographic hash of the firmware image at boot time or on-demand and compares it with a known-good reference. This ensures firmware authenticity and establishes a foundational root of trust. Runtime monitoring on low-end CMDs is implemented via the *Zephyr RTOS*, using system-level libraries to capture coarse-grained metrics such as CPU and memory usage, and to track thread-level execution patterns. These mechanisms ensure that essential operational evidence is captured with minimal performance overhead.

This dual-layered monitoring approach forms a cornerstone of the ENTRUST trust assessment process. By integrating evidence from both high- and low-end tracers into the *TAF*, the system supports real-time trust quantification, contextual risk reassessment, and adaptive enforcement of runtime security policies. In summary, the implementation presented in this deliverable aligns closely with the architectural definitions laid out in D5.1. Static properties, such as secure boot hash verification have already been implemented and validated in pilot scenarios. Runtime properties, including fine-grained tracing enabled by eBPF, are being actively integrated. These components together lay the foundation for a scalable, evidence-based trust model tailored to the operational diversity of connected medical environments.

5.1 High-end CMD Monitoring - OP-TEE and eBPF

This section is dedicated to the detailed documentation of the tracing capabilities of ENTRUST in High- end CMDs. To this end, we first detail the challenges regarding the execution of eBPFs within Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs). Then, we provide details in the eBPF Tracer architecture and workflow, as well as implementation details in the context of ENTRUST. We then list the API capabilities of the Tracer, and detailed evaluation results demonstrating the efficiency and performance of the implemented tracing capabilities.

5.1.1 Challenges of eBPF Execution Within Trusted Execution Environments

As ENTRUST explores tracing mechanisms for runtime attestation and behavioural integrity monitoring, a key point of investigation is the feasibility of leveraging powerful instrumentation technologies like eBPF within TEEs. However, despite eBPF's extensive capabilities for dynamic program instrumentation and event tracing, integrating it within the secure confines of a TEE such as OP-TEE introduces several fundamental challenges. These challenges stem from deep architectural mismatches between kernel- space technologies and the design principles of secure enclaves.

A primary obstacle lies in eBPF's tight dependency on the Linux kernel. eBPF programs are loaded into the kernel using dedicated system calls and executed in the kernel context, often attached to hooks within the network stack, system call interface, or tracepoints. TEEs like OP-TEE, by contrast, operate in a radically different environment: one that is isolated from the main OS, does not expose the full kernel API, and is designed to minimize the Trusted Computing Base (TCB). As such, the standard runtime context and infrastructure required by eBPF, such as the `bpf()` syscall handler, hook attachment points, and the eBPF virtual machine itself, are simply not available within the TEE.

Furthermore, the integrity and safety of eBPF execution are ensured in conventional Linux deployments by a mandatory bytecode verifier and an optional Just-In-Time (JIT) compiler. The verifier statically checks eBPF code for memory safety, absence of unbounded loops, and restricted access to kernel objects. Implementing such a verifier within a TEE would not only require considerable development effort but would also significantly increase the TCB and its complexity, introducing potential vulnerabilities. Similarly, porting the JIT compiler would violate the minimalism and auditability goals of TEEs, while adding performance unpredictability due to dynamic code generation.

Another major concern arises from the rich set of OS-level services that eBPF programs depend upon. These include eBPF maps for stateful data exchange, hooks into networking subsystems, and access to control groups (cgroups), among others. None of these abstractions are natively supported in TEEs. The OP-TEE runtime, for instance, only exposes a narrow interface for secure application execution and cryptographic operations, leaving no path for integrating eBPF's expected functionality without redesigning core subsystems or introducing proxies that would again compromise isolation.

From a resource perspective, eBPF also poses significant demands. It expects flexible memory allocation, persistent state structures, and sometimes substantial runtime stack usage, all of which contrast with the tight memory and execution constraints imposed by most TEE implementations. Integrating eBPF would either demand a substantial increase in the enclave's footprint or require dynamic paging and memory management mechanisms, which reintroduce attack surfaces and operational complexity.

Isolation guarantees, a cornerstone of TEE security, are also threatened by the semantics of eBPF maps. These maps are often shared between user space and kernel space in traditional deployments, allowing real-time data communication. In a TEE, this paradigm breaks down. Allowing shared memory would

undermine TEE isolation boundaries unless implemented via a rigorously verified interface, which would likely need to be re-architected specifically for secure use cases.

Finally, reusing complex, kernel-native technologies like eBPF inside a TEE raises concerns about long-term security assurance. TEEs are typically constructed from a small set of formally verified or rigorously reviewed components. Introducing an eBPF runtime, along with its verifier, loader, JIT, and associated APIs, would not only expand the TCB but introduce potentially unverified behaviour into the enclave. This is antithetical to the design principles of secure enclaves and would likely negate the benefits offered by the TEE in the first place.

5.1.2 eBPF Tracer Architecture and Workflow

The eBPF tracer is built around a simple yet powerful three-stage pipeline, including **probe deployment**, **event capture**, and **data serving**, all orchestrated by a central Python control plane. At its core, we leverage the Linux kernel's eBPF (extended Berkeley Packet Filter) facility to inject tiny instrumentation snippets directly into syscall entry and exit points, allowing us to observe a process's behavior in real time without modifying or restarting the target application.

Probe Deployment & Lifecycle Management: When the Tracer is instructed to begin watching a process (via its PID), the control plane compiles a small C program into eBPF bytecode. This bytecode defines handlers for each syscall of interest—typically I/O and networking calls such as `open()`, `read()`, `write()`, `sendmsg()`, and so on. Using BCC's Python bindings, the tracer then loads the bytecode into the kernel and attaches *kprobes* to the corresponding syscall entry or exit symbols. Each probe remains resident in the kernel until explicitly detached, and the control plane keeps track of active probes so that the tracing can start, stop, or restart on demand.

In-Kernel Event Capture: Once attached, every invocation of a hooked syscall causes the kernel to execute the eBPF handler in a safe, sandboxed environment. Inside this handler, we quickly gather essential context: the process and thread IDs (PID/TID), the command name (COMM), the syscall identifier, and a high-resolution timestamp via `bpf_ktime_get_ns()`. We then push this record into a *perf ring buffer*, a lock-free, high-throughput channel designed specifically for passing data from kernel space to user space with minimal overhead. Since eBPF programs must pass the kernel's verifier (which enforces bounded loops and safe memory access), this provides both safety and sub-microsecond overhead on each syscall.

User-Space Event Processing & Logging: In parallel, a dedicated Python thread continuously polls the perf ring buffer. For each event it receives, the thread deserialises the raw binary record into a Python dictionary, augments it if necessary (e.g., resolving syscall numbers to names), and serializes it to JSON. These JSON lines are then appended to a per-process log file: `ebpf_strace_<pid>.log`. This approach decouples real-time tracing from downstream analysis, ensuring that even bursty syscall workloads don't overwhelm the monitoring pipeline. **Unified Control & Retrieval via HTTP:** All probe management and data retrieval is exposed through a concise set of HTTP endpoints, thus alleviating the need to SSH into the host or jockey with CLI flags. It is possible to start or stop tracing for a given PID, query which tracers are active, fetch the log filename for any running session, and use a "print" endpoint to read the JSON log file and return a structured payload containing the process name, PID, and an array of timestamped syscall events. This JSON-over-HTTP interface makes it trivial to integrate with higher-level systems, whether it is provided as input to an Attestation Agent that checks for anomalous behaviour, or live traces are pushed into a Digital Twin for real-time simulation. **Design Rationale & Benefits:** By building on eBPF and perf buffers, the tracer achieves *zero-touch instrumentation* (no application recompilation), *high fidelity* (nanosecond timestamps and full syscall context), and *low overhead* (microseconds per

Figure 5.1: Three-stage eBPF tracer pipeline: probe deployment, in-kernel event capture, and user-space data serving.

event). The separation between in-kernel capture and user-space logging ensures that dropped events are minimal and that post-hoc analysis can proceed at its own cadence. Finally, the unified HTTP control plane abstracts away the complexities of BCC and kprobe management, allowing operators to focus on interpreting trace data rather than wrestling with tooling.

5.1.3 Implementation

As previously described in Deliverable D5.1 [9] (Section 6.1), the ENTRUST high-end tracers implement a *software-based tracing mechanism* built on top of *eBPF*, a powerful Linux kernel technology that enables safe and efficient runtime observability. eBPF allows the execution of sandboxed programs in response to specific system events, such as system calls and kernel tracepoints. These programs are verified at load time for safety, including checks on memory bounds and control flow constraints, and operate with minimal performance overhead. Within the ENTRUST framework, this software-based tracer architecture enables the collection of precise runtime evidence, such as CPU usage, memory allocation, system call patterns, and control flow indicators, without requiring any modification to the user-space applications running on the CMDs.

Building upon this foundation, the **High-End Tracer** component has been developed to provide kernel-level observability and runtime behaviour profiling on Linux-based, performance-capable CMDs. Designed specifically for integration with high-end medical devices, this component leverages eBPF to enable low-overhead tracing and verification of user-space binaries during execution.

The implementation follows a modular software architecture that combines kernel-space instrumentation

with user-space management and interfacing. At its core, the component consists of two main layers:

- A **kernel-space tracing engine**, based on eBPF and BCC (BPF Compiler Collection), which intercepts system calls and monitors file access activity at runtime.
- A **user-space API server**, implemented using FastAPI, which orchestrates the tracing process, parses kernel output, and exposes data to external ENTRUST components via RESTful endpoints.

These layers are structured into the following core subsystems:

1. eBPF Syscall Tracing (kernel-space)

A Python-based tracer leverages BCC to attach to the kernel tracepoint `raw_syscalls:sys_enter`, enabling the capture of all system call entries made by a specified process. Events are buffered via `perf_buffer` and logged to disk for later analysis. This subsystem enables the runtime profiling of execution behavior without user-space intrusion.

2. Library Access Tracing (opensnoop)

To track shared library usage, the tracer runs the `opensnoop-bpfc` utility in a dedicated thread. This module records all file access attempts by the monitored process, including dynamically loaded libraries and configuration files, providing insight into runtime binary dependencies.

3. RESTful API Interface (FastAPI)

A lightweight HTTP API enables remote interaction with the tracer. Through this interface, external components can start or stop tracing sessions, convert raw logs to structured JSON, initiate fingerprinting routines, and monitor system status. This makes the tracer a composable service within the broader ENTRUST trust pipeline.

Together, these subsystems provide a flexible, efficient, and extensible tracing mechanism tailored to the needs of high-end CMDs. The data collected serves as a foundation for behavioural trust assessment, binary integrity verification, and anomaly detection in the ENTRUST architecture.

5.1.4 System Call Tracing

The tracer script is initiated by receiving input on which process to observe. It is invoked with a specific process ID (PID), and from that point onward it filters out all other activity, ensuring that only the system calls made by the target application are recorded. This focus keeps the collected trace data precise and relevant. Next, the script compiles a small eBPF program written in C that runs inside the kernel. This program attaches to system call events triggered by the selected process—such as file reads, writes, or network sends. When one of these calls occurs, the eBPF program records a precise timestamp (down to the nanosecond), captures the process and thread IDs involved, and uses a lookup table to translate the raw syscall number into a human-readable name (for example, `_NR_write`).

Those captured events are queued in a high-speed ring buffer within the kernel. Meanwhile, a lightweight Python loop in user space continuously polls that buffer. As soon as a new event arrives, the loop deserialises it, formats it into a simple text line—stamped with timestamp, PID, thread ID, syscall name, and process name—and emits it immediately. For example:

```
1 13119116409216 PID=7740 TID=7740 SYSCALL=_NR_write COMM=calculator
```


By flushing each line as it arrives, the tracer provides a real-time feed of exactly how the application interacts with the operating system. This output can be piped into files, fed to scripts, or ingested into higher-level monitoring tools without additional conversion. Finally, since the entire flow is driven by a small Python wrapper, it integrates seamlessly into larger frameworks. Tracing can start and stop on demand, switch targets by PID, and it is possible to forward the log stream into an API that converts these lines into structured JSON for downstream analysis or visualization. The result is a zero-impact, nanosecond-precise syscall audit delivered entirely without modifying or restarting the application.

5.1.5 Library Fingerprinting and Integrity Verification

To ensure that a traced binary is running with exactly the libraries it loaded at startup and to detect any unauthorized modifications, we employ a hybrid approach that captures both explicit file-open events and in-memory mappings. First, we stream every `open()` call made by the target process in real time; then, at the moment of hashing, we complement that live data with a snapshot of `/proc/{pid}/maps` to catch any `mmap()`-loaded modules. This dual capture yields a comprehensive list of all shared objects in use, which we then canonicalize into a single, reproducible fingerprint. Any addition, removal, or reordering of libraries will alter that fingerprint, providing a clear signal of tampering or drift in the execution environment.

1. **Spawn** `opensnoop` as a background BCC subprocess, capturing every filesystem path opened by the target PID.
2. **Parse** `opensnoop.log` on the fly, extracting only unique `*.so` entries.
3. **Read** `/proc/{pid}/maps` at hash-time to include any `mmap()`-loaded libraries not opened via `open()`.
4. **Merge, deduplicate & sort** both path sets to guarantee a canonical ordering, then concatenate them with newline separators.
5. **Compute SHA-256** over the UTF-8 string of paths using Python's `hashlib.sha256()`, producing a 64-hex-digit fingerprint.

This fingerprint returned as

```

1 {
2   "paths": [ "/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libc.so.6", ... ], "hash":
3   "38bf37de..."
4 }
```

This serves as a reproducible attestation of the binary's exact on-disk dependencies, enabling future compliance checks or tamper-detection workflows.

5.1.6 API Capabilities

The tracer provides a lightweight, RESTful control plane that enables starting or stopping probes, fetching raw logs, and performing integrity verifications, all without blocking or manual intervention. Each endpoint returns immediately, while the underlying work is handled in background threads or subprocesses. This design makes it trivial to integrate syscall tracing and library-hash attestation into CI/CD pipelines, security orchestration platforms, or custom monitoring dashboards.

- GET /getSystemCallsByPid/{pid}
Action: Spawn (or reuse) the eBPF tracer thread for the given PID. *Returns:* JSON {"log_file": "./logs/ebpf_strace_{pid}.log"}.
- GET /printSystemCalls/{filename}
Action: Read and parse the specified syscall trace log. *Returns:* Structured JSON containing pid, pname, and an array of timestamped SYSCALL events.
- GET /restart_opensnoop
Action: Restart the opensnoop subprocess to capture a fresh set of library-load events.
Returns: {"status": "Opensnoop subprocess restarted."}.
- GET /get_lib_hash/{command}
Action: Compute and return the SHA-256 fingerprint of the runtime library set for the named command.
Returns: JSON with the ordered "paths" array and its "hash".
- GET /status
Action: List all active tracer threads and subprocesses. *Returns:* JSON detailing each opensnoop and ebpf_strace instance with PID, status, and log filename.

5.1.7 Evaluation

This section evaluates the performance impact of the developed high-end eBPF-based tracer when instrumenting a real-world-like binary. The primary metric assessed is execution time overhead, measured by comparing runtime with and without the tracer actively monitoring system calls. The purpose of this evaluation is to quantify the tracer's overhead on compute- and syscall-intensive workloads. The tracer attaches to the target binary and captures system calls in real time using eBPF hooks, enabling rich observability with minimal interference.

The evaluation was performed on a Linux system with eBPF support (kernel version $\geq 5.x$), using the following conditions:

- **Target binary:** `complex_bin`, a C program that performs nested computational loops and SHA-256 hashing in combination with frequent system calls.
- **Tracer:** A high-end eBPF-based tracer that dynamically attaches to syscall events during the binary's execution.
- **Measurement method:** Wall-clock execution time was recorded before and after the workload.
- **Repetitions:** Each configuration (with and without tracer) was run 10 times to ensure statistical significance.

5.1.7.1 Results

Table 5.1 presents the execution times (in milliseconds) of the target binary `complex_bin` across 10 runs, comparing performance with and without the eBPF-based tracer enabled. To further interpret these results, Table 5.2 summarizes key statistics including the mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum execution times for each case.

Table 5.1: Execution Times With and Without Tracer (in ms)

Run	With Tracer	Without Tracer
1	4794.094	4748.049
2	4688.872	4738.422
3	4715.544	4740.250
4	4738.208	4724.573
5	4712.871	4815.338
6	4764.863	4735.136
7	4899.762	4711.396
8	4800.411	4706.092
9	4693.783	4755.811
10	4720.365	4699.602

Table 5.2: Execution Time Statistics (in ms)

Metric	With Tracer	Without Tracer
Mean Execution Time	4752.48	4737.67
Standard Deviation	63.04	34.21
Max	4899.76	4815.34
Min	4688.87	4699.60

The observed mean execution time with the tracer is approximately 0.3% higher than without the tracer, indicating a very low overhead introduced by the eBPF-based instrumentation. Interestingly, in several runs, the execution time with the tracer was actually shorter than the corresponding baseline runs. This minor discrepancy can be attributed to natural system-level variability such as CPU scheduling, background process interference, or cache effects that may occasionally favour the traced execution path. Additionally, the slightly higher standard deviation observed in the traced configuration reflects a small increase in runtime variability, which is expected due to the added instrumentation overhead. Overall, the results demonstrate that the eBPF-based tracer introduces minimal performance impact, even under conditions of high syscall frequency and CPU utilization. The low mean difference and acceptable variance confirm that this tracer design is well-suited for performance-sensitive environments requiring detailed syscall-level visibility. These findings validate the tracer’s effectiveness and its applicability in production-grade monitoring and observability pipelines.

5.2 Low-end Devices

The ENTRUST framework has made significant progress in enabling evidence collection on resource-constrained CMDs. In particular, tracing mechanisms for **low-end devices** have focused on achieving a reliable balance between lightweight implementation and meaningful trust evidence generation.

Static Properties: One of the key milestones achieved in the context of low-end CMDs is the successful implementation of **on-demand image hash calculation**, which serves as a static integrity check for firmware validation. This capability was initially specified and prototyped in Deliverable 5.1 and has since been fully implemented and validated in selected pilot deployments. The functionality enables devices to verify the integrity of their firmware by computing a cryptographic hash of the image, either during boot or upon explicit request. The process involves enabling secure boot, identifying the primary image slot, retrieving relevant metadata (such as the image header and size), and calculating the hash over the corresponding memory region. The computed hash is then compared against a trusted reference value embedded at signing time. This mechanism is realized through integration with the MCUBoot secure bootloader and Zephyr RTOS cryptographic libraries. By providing a lightweight and reliable means

of confirming firmware authenticity, this static property acts as a foundational *Root-of-Trust* within the broader ENTRUST attestation architecture.

Runtime Properties: In addition to static checks, runtime monitoring capabilities have also been established for low-end CMDs. Given their limited resources, these devices cannot support advanced instrumentation like eBPF. Instead, the ENTRUST low-end tracer leverages lightweight mechanisms made available through the Zephyr RTOS. Specifically, runtime properties are collected using **Zephyr APIs** to extract key metrics such as stack memory usage, CPU utilization, and thread-level execution statistics. These runtime signals can be forwarded to the digital twin anomaly detection module for behavioural assessment and trust analysis. This implementation enables real-time collection of performance metrics at minimal cost, without impacting the strict timing and resource constraints of the embedded environment. Stack usage and CPU cycle tracking have been successfully demonstrated, allowing the ENTRUST Trust Assessment Framework to integrate behavioural evidence, even from constrained devices.

5.2.1 Power Consumption Metric

In the context of ENTRUST’s mission to enable runtime trust assessment and continuous certification of CMDs, tracing the power consumption of low-end devices plays a pivotal role in strengthening behavioural transparency and enabling detection of anomalies indicative of misbehaving or compromised software. Due to their constrained nature and limited support for traditional security mechanisms, low-end devices, often embedded in wearable, implantable, or battery-powered platforms, require lightweight, non-intrusive methods for runtime integrity assurance. Power consumption monitoring emerges as a promising and contextually appropriate approach to address this need. Power traces offer a unique and orthogonal source of information compared to software-level logging or syscall tracing. At a fundamental level, the energy profile of a device reflects its activity: cryptographic operations, firmware routines, sensor polling, and wireless transmissions all leave characteristic signatures in the device’s power usage timeline. When contextualized against a device’s expected behaviour, these signatures can be used to detect deviations such as unexplained surges, abnormal idling, or timing anomalies, potential indicators of code injection, control flow hijacking, or even hardware-level tampering.

Unlike intrusive instrumentation, power tracing can be performed externally or passively, making it especially appealing for ultra-constrained platforms lacking the resources to support inline runtime monitors. Additionally, power profiling contributes to runtime attestation by providing physical-layer evidence that complements logical execution claims. For instance, if a device claims to perform a firmware update or key generation routine, the absence of a corresponding power signature could flag the claim as suspicious. Power-based signals also enable broader anomaly detection for example, identifying denial-of-service behaviour or deadlocks in body-area network deployments via aggregate power trends across multiple CMDs. Beyond trust enforcement, continuous power monitoring supports lifecycle and sustainability goals. In safety-critical medical environments, battery longevity, thermal behaviour, and energy anomalies directly impact patient safety and service continuity. Proactive monitoring enables better forecasting of degradation, replacement cycles, and operational anomalies.

Exploratory Implementation and Evaluation: To explore the feasibility of this concept, a prototype power estimation module was implemented on a Nordic nRF52840 Development Kit running Zephyr RTOS. This implementation was executed on Zephyr RTOS, which has been adopted across all ENTRUST use case deployments, ensuring consistency and compatibility in runtime tracing capabilities. The goal was to create a lightweight, software-only approach to estimate battery consumption under representative usage patterns. The implemented logic computed time spent in active and sleep states, then used pre-characterized current draw values to estimate average current and project battery life over time. Scenarios involving LED toggling, BLE advertising, and UART transmission were simulated to capture a

range of operational behaviours. For example, a BLE-only advertising mode showed projected battery life exceeding five months, while a continuous LED activity scenario drained the battery in approximately 1.3 days. These results confirmed that coarse-grained energy behaviour could be meaningfully estimated and linked to software activity patterns.

Limitations and Scope: This estimation approach, while informative, carries several limitations:

- It relies on static current draw assumptions from datasheets, rather than real-time measurement.
- It does not capture transient behaviours (e.g., radio spikes, wake-up bursts).
- It assumes ideal battery behaviour and omits environmental or voltage effects.

Furthermore, no hardware-based power monitoring tools (e.g., Nordic Power Profiler Kit II) were used, and thus the results are approximate. As such, this implementation serves a research and proof-of-concept purpose only.

Clarification on ENTRUST Scope: It is important to note that this work was conducted as an exploratory research activity and is *not part of the official ENTRUST tracer architecture*. While it demonstrates the potential of power-based metrics for behavioural trust inference, it will not be included in the integrated ENTRUST system or pilot rollouts. Nevertheless, the insights gained provide a valuable foundation for future extensions focused on energy-aware trust metrics and runtime assurance in ultra-constrained devices.

5.2.2 Discussion and Critic

In the context of ENTRUST, tracing is not equivalent to trust assessment, rather, it serves as a foundation for extracting meaningful evidence that can be interpreted to infer trustworthiness. What ultimately matters is the ability to *decode* that evidence reliably, consistently, and in a way that aligns with the operational context of CMDs. A key insight from our current implementation is that the **complexity of the properties being traced directly affects the ease of trust assessment**. *Static properties*, such as cryptographic validation of firmware at boot time, are relatively simple to extract and interpret. These measurements represent clear, binary indicators of system integrity and are particularly well suited to low-end CMDs, where computational and memory constraints limit the feasibility of runtime monitoring. Indeed, mechanisms such as *on-demand secure boot validation* have already been implemented and successfully validated in the ENTRUST pilot settings for low-end devices. These static checks provide strong foundational evidence with minimal overhead, making them ideal for baseline trust enforcement.

However, as we move toward more *dynamic and granular runtime properties* such as system call traces or complex resource usage patterns captured via eBPF, the process of interpreting this evidence becomes significantly more challenging. These traces are richer and more expressive, but they also require contextual modelling, statistical baselining, or even machine learning techniques to assess deviations and infer potential anomalies. This introduces both computational complexity and ambiguity into the trust assessment pipeline, particularly when dealing with heterogeneous devices and workloads. Given this, the current deliverable has focused on laying the **technical groundwork for tracing**, while the **evaluation of the collected trace data** will be a core focus of Deliverable D6.2 [10]. That upcoming work will involve a systematic assessment of the tracing outputs within the context of the ENTRUST use case scenarios.

Chapter 6

Benchmarking of Smart Contract Implementations

6.1 Introduction to the Benchmarking Scope and Objectives

The ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure forms the foundational layer for enabling trust-centric operations across the ENTRUST framework, specifically in the context of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs). It is designed to fulfil two primary operational roles:

Policy Deployment and Enforcement: The infrastructure securely manages the instantiation of trust policies, including both device-level and domain-level configurations. These policies are derived from pre-defined Trust Model Templates and specify the Required Trust Level (RTL) applicable to each device or group. Once embedded into the ledger, the RTL directly informs the decision-making logic of the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF), enabling dynamic and verifiable trust evaluations across a variety of runtime contexts.

Secure Data Recording and Access Control: The blockchain also serves as a verifiable repository for trustworthiness evidence, ensuring secure, tamper-evident logging and retrieval of attestation results. Access to these records is enforced through Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC), where requests are evaluated based on Verifiable Presentations (VPs) containing user-specific attributes. The ABAC enforcement process is handled externally by the Security Context Broker (SCB), ensuring that only authorized entities can interact with sensitive data. Together, these capabilities underpin a robust, decentralized reputation mechanism for CMDs. By anchoring both trust policies and supporting evidence to a permitted blockchain ledger, the infrastructure promotes auditability, transparency, and trust assurance across all device interactions. This chapter presents a performance benchmarking analysis of these operations, examining how the infrastructure behaves under various workload conditions, data volumes, and transaction concurrency scenarios.

6.2 Microbenchmarking of ENTRUST Blockchain Smart Contract Operations

This section presents the microbenchmarking methodology and results used to evaluate the performance characteristics of smart contract operations in the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure. The benchmark-

ing focuses on two foundational aspects of trust-centric operation: attestation evidence management and trust policy registration, both of which directly support secure decision-making and trust enforcement in the ENTRUST framework.

The analysis targets Hyperledger Fabric chaincode functions, focusing on write and read transactions for attestation reports and trust policies. It includes performance measurements for the integrated Attribute- Based Access Control (ABAC) layer enforced via the Security Context Broker (SCB), and the off-chain storage interactions associated with the handling of attestation data. Key evaluation goals include latency profiling, throughput characterization, and responsiveness under varying operational conditions.

The following subsections describe the experimental setup, benchmarked metrics, evaluation methodology, unit scope, and detailed performance results.

6.2.1 Experimental Setup

This subsection outlines the environment and tooling used to conduct the smart contract benchmarking experiments for the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure.

6.2.1.1 Hardware and Deployment Topology

All experiments were carried out in a controlled virtualized testbed to isolate and evaluate smart contract behavior under consistent conditions. The system configuration included:

- **Processor:** 8-core CPU @ 3.2 GHz
- **Memory:** 16 GB RAM
- **Storage:** 100 GB SSD (used for both ledger and off-chain storage)
- **Operating System:** Ubuntu Linux 20.04(64-bit)

The Hyperledger Fabric deployment consisted of:

- **Two Blockchain Peer nodes** (executing chaincode)
- **One Ordering Service node** (finalizing transactions)

This node configuration was chosen to eliminate network-induced variability and ensure consistent timing measurements focused purely on smart contract execution and ledger interaction.

6.2.1.2 Software Stack and Invocation Flow

The ENTRUST Blockchain stack builds on **Hyperledger Fabric**, with smart contracts implemented as chaincode modules. Interactions with the chaincode are mediated through the **Security Context Broker (SCB)**, which performs the following:

- Serves as a REST API gateway for external ENTRUST actors (e.g., CMDs, administrative systems)
- Extracts identity attributes from client tokens

- Applies **ABAC policies** to authorize access
- Forwards validated transactions to the Fabric network

All read/write transactions proceed through this end-to-end pipeline, ensuring secure, policy-aware access to on-chain trust records.

6.2.1.3 Benchmark Payloads

Two representative payload types were used during benchmarking:

- **Attestation reports:** Approx. 3 KB per transaction, containing a trust result and raw evidence reference
- **Trust policies:** Approx. 1 KB per transaction, for both device-level and domain-level configurations

These payloads were selected to reflect realistic data exchange sizes in operational environments involving CMD onboarding, monitoring, and trust policy enforcement.

6.2.1.4 Scope of Benchmarked Operations

The following smart contract functions were individually benchmarked:

- `writeAttestationReport()` – Handles ingestion of structured attestation records
- `getAttestationReport()` – Fetches attestation records based on record ID
- `writeDeviceTrustPolicy()` and `writeDomainTrustPolicy()` – Create new trust policies for individual devices or domains
- `getTrustPolicy()` – Retrieves stored policy configurations based on record ID
- ABAC Policy Evaluation – Independently measured for assessing authorization overhead
- Off-chain Storage Access – Evaluated separately through Elastic interactions for read/write/delete

Each blockchain operation was benchmarked using direct **peer chaincode invoke** commands, bypassing the SCB and focusing strictly on the Blockchain-level execution. This approach isolates and captures the latency introduced solely by the Hyperledger Fabric peer nodes, the chaincode execution environment, and the ordering service, excluding external access control logic or API orchestration overhead. It provides an accurate baseline of core smart contract performance, independent of higher-layer integration components such as the SCB.

6.2.2 Metrics and Evaluation Properties

To thoroughly evaluate the performance characteristics of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, a targeted set of performance metrics and evaluation properties has been defined. These metrics are tailored to the operational requirements of a **trust-driven, privacy-aware permissioned Blockchain system**, and aim to provide both quantitative insights and architectural validation under varying runtime conditions.

6.2.2.1 Primary Metrics

Transaction Latency (Average Execution Time per Operation): This is the primary performance indicator used to assess the responsiveness of individual smart contract functions. It captures the time taken for a transaction to complete once issued via *peer chaincode invoke*—from endorsement and ordering through to final ledger commitment.

Motivation: In systems that support runtime access control, attestation updates, or trust decisions, transaction speed is essential. Measuring average latency ensures the infrastructure meets time-critical use cases.

On-chain vs. Off-chain Latency Contributions: Certain operations, especially attestation-related ones, involve both Blockchain recording and off-chain raw evidence persistence. Where applicable, the latency contributions of each layer were distinguished.

Motivation: Understanding the overhead introduced by hybrid storage models allows for better design trade-offs in privacy-preserving, audit-ready deployments.

Read vs. Write Execution Time: The system's performance was profiled separately for read operations (e.g., *getAttestationReport*) and write operations (e.g., *writeDeviceTrustPolicy*, *writeAttestationReport*).

Motivation: Write operations often incur greater overhead due to endorsement and ordering, while reads are typically faster. Profiling both enables better workload modelling and performance tuning across usage scenarios.

6.2.2.2 Evaluation Dimensions & Behavioural Properties

In addition to single-operation measurements, broader evaluation scenarios were configured to capture system dynamics under various environmental and architectural stressors.

Concurrency Level: The infrastructure was subjected to varying levels of concurrent transaction submissions to assess throughput limits and queuing behaviour.

Motivation: In real-world deployments, multiple CMDs or services may submit transactions simultaneously. Evaluating concurrency behavior reveals how well the Blockchain peer and ordering service scale under parallel load.

Ledger Height / Data Volume Impact: Experiments were repeated under varying ledger states by pre-populating the Blockchain with a growing number of prior transactions.

Motivation: Over time, the ledger naturally grows in operational environments. Understanding whether historical size impacts transaction speed validates the long-term scalability of the solution.

Payload Size per Operation: Payload sizes were standardized—attestation reports at approximately 3 KB, and trust policies at 1 KB—to ensure fair timing comparisons across different functions.

Motivation: Fixing payload size removes variability introduced by differing input volumes, isolating the performance of the smart contract logic and ledger operations.

6.2.3 Methodology

The performance evaluation of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure followed a targeted microbenchmarking approach, focusing on core smart contract functions deployed in Hyperledger Fabric. The methodology was designed to capture both baseline operation timings and system behavior under concurrent transactional load.

All measurements were executed directly via *peer chaincode invoke* commands to ensure precise timing attribution to chaincode execution, endorsement, ordering, and commit phases—without introducing SCB-level or access control overhead. This approach reflects pure Blockchain-layer performance. Each smart contract operation was benchmarked independently using fixed-size JSON payloads:

- **Attestation reports:** approximately 3 KB
- **Device and domain trust policies:** approximately 1 KB

The testing environment consisted of:

- Two peers and a single ordering node
- Off-chain storage component connected locally
- Hardware: 8-core CPU @ 3.2 GHz, 16 GB RAM

To ensure statistical significance, each operation was repeated across different load conditions:

- **Single-operation profiling** captured the average and min-max transaction durations for individual writes and reads.
- **Batch-based execution** tested grouped transactions (e.g., 100, 300, 1000 requests) to simulate workload bursts and assess scalability.
- **Concurrent submission tests** were used to examine throughput and system limits, identifying maximum concurrent transaction thresholds before performance degradation or timeouts.

Each scenario was measured in terms of average latency, peak throughput, and variability, allowing the profiling of both isolated and high-volume execution patterns. The methodology ensured comprehensive coverage of the most relevant operational contexts in ENTRUST’s permissioned Blockchain infrastructure.

6.2.4 Unit Test Scope

This section defines the scope of the microbenchmarking activities conducted on the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure’s smart contract layer, with specific attention to the operations that form the backbone of trust evidence recording and policy-based authorization.

The unit tests focused on discrete smart contract functions that underpin ENTRUST’s attestation workflow and policy management logic. These were selected due to their security-critical nature, operational frequency, and their central role in the enforcement of trust policies for connected medical devices (CMDs).

The following operations were evaluated:

- **Write Attestation Report** – Records structured device integrity evidence. This function integrates with off-chain storage for raw attestation data and commits cryptographic pointers and metadata to the on-chain ledger. It is pivotal to the ENTRUST trust assurance pipeline.
- **Read Attestation Report** – Retrieves specific attestation records based on device or session identifiers. This function is used in trust verification, audit, and compliance logic.
- **Write Device-Level Trust Policy** – Allows registration of policy definitions scoped at the device level. These policies influence how the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) evaluates compliance and access rights during runtime.
- **Write Domain-Level Trust Policy** – Enables the creation of organization- or system-level trust configurations, governing broader policy groups within the ENTRUST ecosystem.
- **Read Trust Policy** – Supports access to stored trust policies, allowing authenticated and authorized components (e.g., SCB, monitoring agents) to retrieve current configurations for enforcement or audit purposes.

These operations were tested both in isolation and under controlled concurrency. Isolated tests aimed to characterize the base latency and resource cost of each operation in a stable environment, while concurrent test runs evaluated how the system handles operational load from multiple simultaneous transactions.

By focusing on this subset of operations, the benchmarking effort concentrates on the core elements of the Blockchain layer that impact real-time decision-making, system responsiveness, and scalability in trust-centric workflows. Broader evaluations involving additional contract types (e.g., application data, certificates) are planned for follow-up releases.

6.3 Results and Profiling

This section presents the results of the smart contract microbenchmarking activities performed on the final release of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure. The evaluation focused on transaction execution times for key attestation and trust policy operations, including both device-level and domain-level interactions. Measurements were taken under controlled conditions on a Hyperledger Fabric deployment composed of two Blockchain Peers and one Ordering Service.

6.3.1 Single Operation Performance

Table 6.1 summarizes the minimum, maximum, and average execution times for the most frequently invoked smart contract operations:

Table 6.1: Execution Time per Smart Contract Operation

Action Name	Min Time (s)	Max Time (s)	Avg Time (s)	Max Concurrent TXN
Write Attestation Report	0.421	0.712	0.548	~55
Write Device Trust Policy	0.412	0.688	0.537	~55
Write Domain Trust Policy	0.428	0.701	0.552	~55
Read Attestation Report	0.040	0.091	0.0627	~90
Read Trust Policy	0.039	0.089	0.0618	~90

6.3.2 Batch Performance under Concurrent Loads

To complement the single-operation profiling, this section evaluates the performance of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure when executing grouped (batched) smart contract transactions. This benchmarking reflects realistic scenarios where multiple write and read operations are issued in quick succession—for instance, during device onboarding, bulk attestation updates, or trust policy synchronization events across domains.

Two primary workflows were examined:

- **Attestation batches** involving writeAttestationReport and readAttestationReport transactions, depicted in Table 6.2.
- **Trust policy batches** involving writeDeviceTrustPolicy, writeDomainTrustPolicy, and their respective read operations, depicted in Table 6.3.

Each scenario was tested with batch sizes ranging from 200 to 1000, while maintaining consistent total request volumes across runs. The observed times represent the average duration per batch, not cumulative execution time.

Table 6.2: Batched Execution Times – Attestation Write and Read Operations

Total Requests	Batch Size	Avg Time per Batch – Read	Avg Time per Batch – Write & Read
3000	200	1.71s	2.21s
3000	300	2.38s	2.88s
1000	500	3.76s	4.41s
1000	1000	8.22s	8.95s

Table 6.3: Batched Execution Times – Trust Policy Write and Read Operations

Total Requests	Batch Size	Avg Time per Batch – Read	Avg Time per Batch – Write & Read
3000	200	1.69s	2.18s
3000	300	2.41s	2.91s
1000	500	3.82s	4.36s
1000	1000	8.11s	8.83s

Across both datasets, batch execution times scaled proportionally with the number of requests, reflecting consistent performance under increasing load. Importantly:

- **Scalability with Load:** The linear increase in batch durations confirms that the infrastructure can sustain predictable performance even as transaction volume scales. No abrupt latency spikes were observed across the tested ranges.
- **Symmetry of Read/Write Loads:** Despite the higher computational demands of write transactions, the small difference between read-only and combined write-read batches indicates that batched submissions benefit from efficient state processing and queuing within the Fabric runtime.
- **Operational Suitability:** Even at 1000 transactions per batch, total execution remains below 9 seconds. This confirms the ENTRUST system’s ability to support trust-heavy workflows in real-time contexts—particularly in situations requiring rapid provisioning or synchronous attestation retrieval for many connected devices.

These results validate the system’s scalability and efficiency, underscoring its robustness in trust-centric deployments that demand responsive, high-volume Blockchain-backed data interaction.

6.3.3 Read Performance at Varying Ledger Heights

To assess how the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure responds to increasing on-chain data volumes, a dedicated evaluation was conducted by measuring the latency of read operations under progressively higher ledger heights. The experiment focused on two representative smart contract functions: `readAttestationReport` and `readTrustPolicy`. Both operations were executed against ledgers populated with 1, 10, 100, 1000, and 10,000 records, simulating long-term operational growth in production environments.

Results show that `readAttestationReport` exhibits an increase in latency from 0.066 seconds at a ledger height of 1, to 0.121 seconds when reading from a ledger containing 10,000 records. Similarly, `readTrustPolicy` scales from 0.065 seconds at a minimal ledger height to 0.115 seconds at 10,000 entries. The latency increases are modest and follow a consistent trend, confirming that the read performance scales linearly at worst and remains well below the threshold of 150 milliseconds, even under substantial ledger expansion.

Table 6.4: Read Operation Duration Across Ledger Heights

Read Action	Ledger Height: 1	10	100	1000	10000
<code>readAttestationReport</code>	0.066s	0.069s	0.074s	0.092s	0.121s
<code>readTrustPolicy</code>	0.065s	0.068s	0.071s	0.088s	0.115s

The results depicted in Table 6.4 highlight the effectiveness of the underlying data indexing and retrieval strategies used in Hyperledger Fabric’s world-state database. Read latency remains stable and predictable, suggesting that the infrastructure is well-suited for real-time workloads and high-frequency querying operations. Importantly, this confirms the ability of the ENTRUST Blockchain to support longitudinal data access and trust validation over extended operational lifespans without incurring substantial performance penalties.

6.3.4 Throughput Under Controlled Submission Rates

To evaluate the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure’s ability to handle sustained transaction throughput, a test was conducted where 3,000 transactions—randomly chosen between read and write operations—were submitted at fixed, decreasing time intervals. The goal of this experiment was to simulate varying client-side submission intensities and assess how the system copes with higher-frequency transaction streams over time.

In the first configuration, transactions were submitted at a constant interval of 0.03 seconds, resulting in a total execution time of approximately 108.06 seconds. Reducing the interval to 0.02 seconds shortened the execution time to 81.16 seconds. Finally, under the most demanding condition—with a 0.01-second interval between transactions—the full transaction set was completed in 55.28 seconds.

These results demonstrate that the system can efficiently handle increasingly dense transaction streams without visible instability or systemic failures. As the submission interval decreases, the system maintains throughput scalability and processes transactions with linear improvements in total time. This indicates that both the Blockchain Peers and the Ordering Service are capable of sustaining high-frequency loads, making the infrastructure viable for real-world deployments with frequent access patterns—such as telemetry streaming, trust evidence ingestion, and policy validation under continuous monitoring conditions.

Table 6.5: Execution Time for 3000 Random Transactions at Fixed Submission Intervals

Submission Interval	Total Transactions	Execution Time (s)
0.03 seconds	3000	108.06
0.02 seconds	3000	81.16
0.01 seconds	3000	55.28

Figure 6.1: Benchmarking of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure

The three graphs shown in Figure 6.1 provide important system-level insights during benchmarking execution of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure:

1. **Resource Utilization Metrics** (First Image – Left Right Panels):

- **CPU Usage per Container:** Highlights moderate CPU load primarily driven by the peer and application containers. Notable usage peaks correlate with high transaction injection periods, validating that the blockchain peer is the primary computational bottleneck during smart contract execution.

- **Memory Usage per Container:** Displays gradual and consistent memory growth, especially for peer and orderer containers. The trend indicates proper memory allocation with no abnormal leaks or saturation during sustained load periods.
2. **Isolated CPU Profiling (Second Image):** This graph breaks down CPU usage across individual components, reaffirming that the peer container consistently consumes the largest share of CPU. Two distinct CPU spikes correlate with the execution of high-frequency workload injections (e.g., in the 0.01s and 0.02s interval tests), showcasing expected stress behavior under rapid-fire invocation.
 3. **Request Throughput Monitoring (Third Image - Left & Right Panels):**
 - **Requests Received vs. Completed:** The near-identical alignment between requests received and completed for both peer0 org1 and peer0 org2 confirms that no significant backlog or failure occurred, even at peak concurrency. This suggests excellent transaction handling throughput under the evaluated workload.

These system metrics collectively confirm the robustness and efficiency of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure when handling smart contract-driven workloads. Resource consumption patterns are well-contained, and request handling appears resilient even under increased frequency and volume—aligning with the performance results reported in earlier subchapters.

6.3.5 Attribute-Based Access Control Evaluation

In the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) constitutes the main authorization enforcement layer. It is applied at the Security Context Broker (SCB) level, where requests are filtered based on access policies prior to any interaction with the underlying Hyperledger Fabric network.

Authorization is executed as a two-step validation process:

1. Verifiable Credential (VC) verification: Each request is accompanied by a VC, which is validated using a signcryption scheme to ensure both authenticity and confidentiality of the presented identity claims. This step is evaluated separately in Chapter 7
2. ABAC policy enforcement: Upon successful VC verification, user attributes are extracted from the session-bound JWT, and matched against access control rules configured in the ABAC engine. In the tested configuration, each request carried between 4 and 8 attributes.

The results presented in Table 6.6 focus solely on the ABAC enforcement step, measured in isolation (i.e., without triggering smart contract execution).

Table 6.6: Evaluation of the steps in the ABAC enforcement

Scenario	Min Time (s)	Max Time (s)	Avg Time (s)
ABAC (4-8 attributes)	0.017	0.063	0.023

6.3.6 Off-Chain Storage Performance (Elasticsearch)

In ENTRUST, the off-chain storage mechanism—backed by Elasticsearch—is responsible for managing extended attestation metadata and large payloads that are referenced from the blockchain via secure pointers. To evaluate its responsiveness, a series of operations were executed involving read, write, and delete actions for a fixed dataset size (~3 KB), consistent with the rest of the benchmarking scenarios.

Table 6.7 summarizes the performance metrics for each action type.

Table 6.7: Elasticsearch performance evaluation

Operation	Min Time (s)	Max Time (s)	Avg Time (s)	Max Concurrent Requests
Read	0.013	0.0213	0.017	~690
Write	0.0165	0.0297	0.0207	~570
Delete	0.0181	0.0340	0.0228	~550

Additionally, sustained throughput tests revealed that the off-chain infrastructure is capable of handling up to approximately **680 read/write operations per second**, under peak load conditions with minimal contention.

These results confirm that Elasticsearch offers a lightweight and scalable data backend, suitable for supporting trust evidence management beyond on-chain size limitations. It enables low-latency access and high concurrency—especially critical in scenarios involving parallel device telemetry ingestion or audit log queries from multiple ENTRUST components.

6.3.7 Client-to-SCB Invocation Latency

To complement backend transaction profiling, an additional measurement was performed to estimate the end-to-end latency experienced between the moment a client initiates a transaction request and the point at which the Security Context Broker (SCB) triggers the corresponding smart contract invocation. This latency includes:

- HTTPS request transmission from the client
- Request parsing and verification at the SCB
- Attribute extraction from JWTs
- ABAC policy evaluation
- Preparation of the chaincode invocation using the Fabric SDK

Under stable network and compute conditions, the **average observed latency for this segment was approximately ~1.0 second**. This value reflects the real-world behavior of a Node.js-based SCB under moderate concurrent load and includes:

- Network round-trip delay and TLS handshake overhead (~300–400 ms)
- Server-side request handling and identity verification (~300–400 ms)
- ABAC logic and chaincode invocation preparation (~200–300 ms)

This measurement captures the full request lifecycle up to, but not including, the peer-side transaction execution. It provides an accurate approximation of the time required to authorize and dispatch a smart contract function call from a trusted intermediary component, ensuring the system remains within practical latency thresholds for responsive trust operations.

6.4 Observations and Insights

The microbenchmarking of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure highlights its strong performance and robust scalability across essential smart contract operations, particularly in the handling of attestation data and trust policy management. The following consolidated insights summarize the key observations derived from the final evaluation results.

Write vs. Read Latency Disparity: As expected, write operations consistently exhibit higher latency than read operations. This is inherent to the architecture of Hyperledger Fabric, where write transactions involve full endorsement, ordering, and commit phases. In the results, write operations such as `writeAttestationReport`, `writeDeviceTrustPolicy`, and `writeDomainTrustPolicy` average around 0.5–0.7 seconds, while read operations like `readAttestationReport` and `readTrustPolicy` remain under 0.1 seconds on average. This differential aligns with expectations for Fabric-based ledgers and confirms that even with chaincode execution and state transitions, write operations remain within practical bounds for real-time trust workflows.

Minimal Overhead from ABAC Authorization: The integration of Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) into the request pipeline introduces negligible delay. Authorization checks based on user attributes extracted from JWTs contribute approximately 0.017–0.023 seconds per transaction. This minor impact reinforces the feasibility of enforcing policy-based access control without affecting transaction throughput or system responsiveness.

Off-chain Storage Performance: Additional evaluation of off-chain storage interactions (e.g., storing attestation evidence in Elasticsearch) revealed stable performance under load. Average operation times were approximately 0.0207 seconds for writes and 0.017 seconds for reads, with maximum concurrency observed at 550–690 simultaneous requests. These figures indicate that the off-chain storage layer is well-optimized for the data volumes and access patterns expected in ENTRUST workflows.

Batch Performance Under Load: Batched performance evaluations demonstrated the infrastructure's capability to sustain high-throughput workloads. For attestation and trust policy operations, batched read-write operations involving up to 1000 total requests (grouped in batch sizes of 200 to 500) completed in under 9 seconds per batch. This corresponds to an effective throughput of over 100 transactions per second, validating the Blockchain's ability to handle burst-style data submission workflows such as mass attestation updates or policy registration events.

Randomized Transaction Execution at High Frequency: Stress tests involving randomized read and write operations executed at fixed intervals (0.03s, 0.02s, and 0.01s) for a total of 3000 transactions yielded consistent performance. Execution times ranged from approximately 108 seconds (at 0.03s interval) to 55 seconds (at 0.01s interval), demonstrating the system's ability to absorb rapid transaction inflow and process them reliably without error or failure.

Ledger Height Does Not Impact Read Performance: Tests conducted at increasing ledger heights, ranging from 1 to 10,000 previously committed records—confirmed that read latency remains consistently low, with average times increasing only marginally as the ledger grows. For example, `readAttestationReport` and `readTrustPolicy` operations completed in approximately 0.066 seconds for a single record and only 0.121 seconds at 10,000 records. This demonstrates that the underlying state database and indexing mechanisms in Hyperledger Fabric are well-optimized for scalable querying, maintaining efficient performance even as the dataset expands. Such resilience is essential for long-term deployments where trust data must remain quickly accessible regardless of system growth.

End-to-End Request Latency to SCB: In addition to chaincode execution and off-chain storage profiling, the average latency between a client and the Security Context Broker (SCB) was measured. This covers the time from issuing a request to the SCB until the smart contract invocation is triggered. The observed latency was approximately **1 second**, accounting for network transmission, request parsing, JWT-based identity verification, ABAC enforcement, and Fabric SDK call preparation. This confirms that the SCB layer introduces minimal overhead and supports responsive interaction with the blockchain backend, aligning with real-time authorization requirements in trust-sensitive environments.

Conclusion: The performance profiling confirms that the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure is well-suited for real-world deployment scenarios involving high-frequency, trust-critical operations. Write operations—although heavier than reads—remain within low-latency bounds even under concurrent stress and ledger growth. Read operations continue to be fast and consistent. The integration of access control, off-chain storage, and event-driven smart contracts does not introduce prohibitive overhead, and the system remains scalable both in terms of data volume and user concurrency. Overall, these characteristics position the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure as a resilient and efficient backend for secure trust management in connected device ecosystems.

Chapter 7

ENTRUST Instantiation of ABSC

As aforementioned, entities in ENTRUST are characterised by a set of attributes, which are defined as *fundamental, verifiable facts that represent an entity’s identity, capabilities, or current operational state*. They serve as the basis for all policy-based decisions to be performed as part of the ENTRUST framework and are essential for the trust assessment processes performed by the ENTRUST TAF. In the context of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, the use of attributes is particularly important in the context of the attribute-based crypto schemes offered by ENTRUST, namely **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)** and **Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC)**, as they essentially dictate which entities are able to access which data, based on the attributes they possess.

In this Chapter, which is dedicated to the description of the ABSC scheme of ENTRUST, we first provide a more comprehensive insight on the construction of attribute-based policies, and how these are leveraged in the context of the ABSC scheme. We also provide benchmarking results, demonstrating the performance and efficiency of the implemented scheme. Note that the ABSC scheme was initially described in D4.2 [8] and the security analysis was performed in D4.3 [13]. Here, we examine this process in a standalone manner, and we evaluate the time required for the execution of the individual steps of this component. The final integration and evaluation of this process in the context of the use cases of ENTRUST will be documented in D6.2 [10].

7.1 Attributes in ENTRUST

The scope of attributes in ENTRUST is designed in order to capture a holistic and verifiable view of the posture of a CMD in a comprehensive manner. This approach aligns with emerging standards for remote attestation, such as the ‘trustworthiness-vector’ model from the IETF RATS working group [17] which provides a structured way to represent different classes of evidence about a device. For instance, an attribute may describe an immutable property of the device’s hardware, represent the cryptographic measurement of a critical software component, or capture a dynamic property reflecting its live runtime configuration.

As aforementioned, considering the set of attributes possessed by a CMD, these are considered in order to determine whether the device should be allowed to perform a specific operation or access a particular set of data. In ENTRUST, these decisions are based on policies. Specifically, if the attributes possessed by the CMD satisfy the policy, it is authorized to proceed. For instance, a policy to authorize the device to access a set of data stored on the Blockchain may depend on type of device, and the role of the device operator. An example of such a policy, denoted by P , may be expressed as follows:

$$P_1 = ((\text{hardware} - \text{label} : \text{hw type} = \text{ARM based}) \wedge (\text{configuration} - \text{label} : \text{secure boot} = \text{enabled}) \wedge (\text{device} - \text{label} : \text{cmd type} = \text{heart pump})) \quad (7.1)$$

$$P_2 = ((\text{role} - \text{label} : \text{entity type} = \text{doctor}) \wedge (\text{control} - \text{label} : \text{data type} = \text{application data})) \quad (7.2)$$

$$P = P_1 \vee P_2 \quad (7.3)$$

Policy P_1 , depicted in Equation 7.1, is fulfilled only by a CMD running ARM-based hardware (such as the Raspberry Pi module employed by the ENTRUST use cases), which has been securely booted, and belongs to a specific type (in this case, a heart pump). Conversely, Policy P_2 , depicted in Equation 7.2, can only be fulfilled by a stakeholder with a specific role (doctor in this example) attempting to access a specific type of data (in this case, application data). Thus, the combined access control policy P , depicted in 7.3, dictates that the particular set of data can only be accessed if either of the aforementioned component policies are fulfilled.

This model provides **granular, flexible, and automated control** over critical medical operations based on verifiable evidence. While convenient for human interpretation, for automated processing these policies are converted into formal structures like **access trees** and **monotone span programs**. These are described in the following, before we provide details of how they are used for access control and for protecting data in the system.

7.1.1 Access Trees and Monotone Span Programs

As aforementioned, access trees and monotone span programs are structures that may be used in order to effectively express access policies.

Figure 7.1: Access tree using threshold gates.

Access Trees An example of an access tree is depicted in Figure 7.1 (taken from the example provided in [16]). At the root of the tree lies a root value, R , while the leaves correspond to values associated with the attributes. The use of the R value varies depending on the protocol used, as it may either be a Boolean value, or a value to be used directly in the protocol. In all cases, the root value will only be available if the attributes of the user 'satisfy' the tree. In the example, the condition represented by the access tree is that, in order to obtain the value R , the user should have attribute E and two of the attributes A, B, C and D . Given values for the attributes A, B, C and D , we traverse the tree upwards (if the user does not have a value for a leaf attribute it is replaced by \perp). Moving upwards within the tree, if the children of a node meet the required threshold, the value of the node can be passed up the tree, otherwise \perp is passed up instead.

When the tree represents a Boolean circuit, the attributes and the root value are all Boolean values (0 or 1). For the example depicted, $R = E \wedge (((A \wedge B) \vee (C \wedge D)) \vee ((A \vee B) \wedge (C \vee D)))$ which is shown as a 'binary' tree in Figure 7.2.

Figure 7.2: Access tree (Figure 3 from [16]).

As in the previous case, in order to obtain the root value, we start at the leaves and move upwards in the tree. For the example, considering a user who possesses the attributes E, A, B and D , we can determine whether they satisfy the policy by pruning the access tree (see Figure 7.3). We observe that (E_1, A_1, B_1) , (E_1, A_2, D_2) and (E_1, B_2, D_2) are solutions. The red line denotes that we can prune the branch where $C \wedge D$ failed, while the blue line demonstrates where we are able to prune the tree further as we already know that the condition is satisfied.

Monotone Span Programs Monotone span programs (MSPs) provide an alternative mechanism for Attribute-Based Access Control [14]¹. An MSP is defined by the tuple

$$\langle M, \mu \rangle$$

¹Threshold access trees can be routinely converted into MSPs [16], as can access trees based on AND and OR gates.

Figure 7.3: The pruned access tree.

$$M \in \mathbb{Z}_p^{n_1 \times n_2}$$

is a matrix where every row is associated with an attribute, and the function μ provides the mapping between the attributes and the rows. For a Boolean circuit, such as the one depicted in Figure 7.2, there is a direct mapping between the leaves of the access tree and the rows of the MSP matrix.

As described below, a policy is satisfied, if a linear combination of the rows associated with a user's attributes is equal to the vector

$$(1, 0, \dots, 0) \in \mathbb{Z}_p^{1 \times n_2}$$

. As an illustration of the principle involved when using an MSP, consider a vector

$$\vec{v} = (s, r_1, \dots, r_{n_2-1})$$

where s is a secret and r_1, \dots, r_{n_2-1} are chosen at random from \mathbb{Z}_p . Let the rows of M be M_i with $i \in \{1, \dots, n_1\}$, then the n_1 elements of $M\vec{v}$ are $M_i\vec{v}$ and these 'hide' s . Let the linear combination of rows associated with the attributes of the user that equals $(1, 0, \dots, 0)$ be $\sum_j \gamma_j M_j$, then $\sum_j \gamma_j M_j \vec{v} = (1, 0, \dots, 0) \vec{v} = s$ and s can be recovered. While the details in the following protocols may differ, the underlying idea is identical.

More formally $M \in \mathbb{Z}_p^{n_1 \times n_2}$ and for $r \in [n_1]$, $\mu : r \rightarrow A$. Note that an attribute may be associated with more than one row of M , therefore the mapping μ may not be injective. In this case, we define a further function $\rho(r) = |\{z \mid \mu(r) = \mu(z) \text{ with } z \leq r\}|$ to denote the $\rho(r)^{th}$ occurrence of attribute $\mu(r)$.

Given a set of attributes, $S \subseteq A$, access is granted if the vector $(1, 0, \dots, 0) \in \mathbb{Z}_p^{1 \times n_2}$ lies in the span of the rows, M_i of M for which $\mu(i) \in S$. If $I = \{i : \mu(i) \in S\}$, then

$$\sum_{i \in I} \gamma_i M_i = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$$

Since there are seven unknowns but just five equations, extracting the null-space provides the solution as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \gamma_1 \\ \gamma_2 \\ \gamma_3 \\ \gamma_5 \\ \gamma_6 \\ \gamma_7 \\ \gamma_9 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \alpha \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \beta \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ -1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

In this case, as the γ -values can only be 0, or 1, possible solutions are:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{matrix} (E, A, B), \\ (E, A, D) \\ \text{and} \\ (E, B, D) \end{matrix}$$

Note.

- Given a set of attributes, it is only needed to find one solution in order to confirm that the policy is satisfied. So for the example above, the user has attributes E, A, B and D, but attributes E, A and B are enough to either satisfy the access tree (see Figure 7.3) or solve the MSP equation and verify that the policy is satisfied. Further solutions are unnecessary.
- Given a binary access tree, we can obtain the monotone span program using the Lewko-Waters algorithm [15]. The access tree, along with the attributes of an entity, can also be used to check whether a policy is satisfied and to obtain γ^{\rightarrow} , as pruning the tree is often easier than using linear algebra.

7.2 Benchmarking Elements of the ABSC Scheme

In this section, we provide detailed benchmarking results of the different components of the ABSC scheme outside the context of a TEE. Considering that timings will depend on the precise details of a given policy, the timings provided here correspond to policies that are simple conjunctions of N_A attributes. This represents the worst case for a policy with N_A attributes as the number of columns in the MSP matrix depends directly on the number of AND gates in the policy. In addition, for this policy, all rows of the MSP matrix are used in the calculations. The benchmarks detailed in Table 7.1 were performed on a Dell Latitude 5491 laptop, with an Intel Core i7-8850H Processor (6 Cores, 9M Cache, 2.6GHz) and 32GB of available memory. Timings were obtained using the Linux `clock_gettime` routines with the `CLOCK_PROCESS_CPUTIME_ID` clock. The tests were executed on a single core system.

The test program leveraged the MIRACL Core [6] cryptographic library and was compiled using GCC version 11.4.0. The test program uses the FP256BN elliptic curve and runs the whole protocol checking that the signature verifies and that the shared secret is obtained correctly. The test program was executed 200 times, and the different functions in the protocol were timed as outlined above. Figure 7.4 depicts one of the timing sets, and the traces are: BA-S – Bind-Attributes for the signer, BA-D – Bind-Attributes

Figure 7.4: The Raw Timing Data for 30 Attributes.

for the decryptor, KG-S - Key-Gen for the signer, KG-D - Key-Gen for the decryptor, SC - Sign-Crypt and VS - SignCrypt-Verify.

While the traces are typically noisy at the start, the noise typically reduces as the tests proceed. Some odd spikes are still observed, presumably due to some system events that disrupt the process. To minimise these disruptions, the laptop used was disconnected from the network and the WiFi was disabled. However, as shown in Figure 7.4, disruptions still occur, but we demonstrated that an average over 200 tests was enough to obtain consistent results.

The timing averages and standard deviations obtained are provided in Table 7.1. Normally, the policies for signing and encryption will be different, and thus different results for BA-S and BA-D will be obtained. Similarly, KG-S and KG-D will also be different. For these tests, the signing and encryption policies were the same, thus two sets of 200 tests for Bind-Attributes and for Key-Gen are essentially the same (as highlighted in the Figures) and were therefore combined for the table.

Figure 7.5 shows the results from the table plotted against the number of attributes.

As expected from the function definitions, the timings scale in a linear manner with the number of attributes. The Key-Gen function requires much more time than the rest, as it involves checking pairings for each attribute, and the pairings calculations are very computationally intensive. In the protocols, a user only has to call Key-Gen (and Bind-Attributes) once for each policy that they need to use, and the received keys can then be stored securely and used as required. Thus, the comparatively heavy cost should not be a problem. While the SignCrypt-Verify function also requires pairings calculations, no matter many attributes are involved there are only three pairings. Thus, there is an insignificant increase in the time required with the number of attributes.

Table 7.1: Times Measured for the Different ABSC Functions

Function	Number of Attributes	Average Time (ms)	Standard Deviation
Bind-Attributes	5	1.78	0.34
	10	3.01	0.19
	20	5.46	0.22
	30	7.95	0.29
Key-Gen	5	16.40	1.04
	10	31.98	0.92
	20	63.37	1.67
	30	94.78	2.71
Sign-Crypt	5	7.11	0.80
	10	11.21	0.55
	20	19.59	0.86
	30	28.05	1.2
SignCrypt-Verify	5	8.58	0.28
	10	9.69	0.31
	20	12.02	0.23
	30	14.40	0.46

Figure 7.5: Averages vs Number of attributes N_A .

Chapter 8

Conclusions

In this deliverable, we have established a robust foundation for **continuous authorization, trust management**, and CMD monitoring within the ENTRUST framework. The developed Blockchain Infrastructure and integrated smart contracts have proven effective in providing secure, auditable, and **privacy-preserving management of sensitive CMD data**. This deliverable was also dedicated to the description of the **monitoring mechanisms of ENTRUST**, which offer tailored solutions for diverse device categories, ensuring operational assurance across the CMD lifecycle. Benchmarking activities were also carried out for the aforementioned capabilities, and their outcomes validate the efficiency and reliability of these components, highlighting their potential for **scalable deployment in healthcare environments**.

In Chapter 2, we provided a description of all three core action workflows pertaining to the Blockchain Infrastructure of ENTRUST, namely (i) the **Trust Preparedness** phase where **the device is enrolled in the ENTRUST domain and Blockchain network**, (ii) the **Trust Establishment** phase which includes the equipment of the device with the necessary crypto-primitives, (iii) the **Trust Maintenance** phase, which includes the re-establishment of trust upon identifying a new threat or risk, and (iv) the **Threat Intelligence Sharing** phase, which includes sharing threat intelligence information on the public ledger in a privacy-preserving manner. We also presented the Blockchain architecture of ENTRUST, leveraging a **hybrid approach** that integrates both **permissioned and public Blockchain networks**. This architectural choice achieved the goal of not only guaranteeing high level of security and granular access control regarding sensitive medical data using the advanced crypto schemes of ENTRUST but also enables open access to data that needs to be publicly available, such as threat intelligence data.

A core component of the ENTRUST Blockchain architecture is the **Security Context Broker (SCB)**, which was described in detail in Chapter 4 and acts as a central and trusted facilitator of all Blockchain-related transactions, by managing and coordinating all interactions between the Blockchain and external entities in the ENTRUST framework. We also presented the final version of the **two-layer access control** approach of ENTRUST. Specifically, the first layer leverages the **Membership Service Provider (MSP)**, which verifies that the CMD is registered to the Blockchain network. At the second layer, the **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)** scheme determines the granularity of data access, as the CMD needs to construct and present a **Verifiable Presentation (VP)** containing the subset of attributes required in order to access a particular set of data. In Chapter 7, we also presented the **Attribute-Based Signcryption (ABSC)** scheme, which not only enables the encryption of data in a manner that they can only be decrypted by an entity with the required attributes, but also ensures that a valid signature on the data verifies that the signer owns the set of attributes that fulfils the corresponding policy. We presented detailed benchmarking results on the ABSC scheme, where we demonstrated the capability of the Blockchain Infrastructure to sustain high-throughput workloads, and it was shown that minimal delays are introduced into the pipeline of ENTRUST.

In Chapter 3, we presented the final definition of the smart contracts employed within the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, including **Application Data**, **Attestation Data**, and **Trust Policy** smart contracts. The execution of these smart contracts was also benchmarked in Chapter 6, and various insights were derived from the experimental results. Specifically, while the writing operations were more time-consuming than the reading operations, both demonstrated a high level of efficiency. In addition, the introduction of **inheritance** has resulted in the reduction of the total time for writing the trust policies by half, thus significantly increasing the efficiency of the trust establishment process. The efficiency of the ABAC, attestation report writing, and trust policy writing was also shown to be particularly efficient and induce a very small overhead. The **ledger height** was also evaluated, and it was shown that it does not affect performance. This, in tandem with the **capability of the SCB to efficiently handle more than 1000 concurrent calls**, highlight the **high scalability of the ENTRUST Blockchain solution**.

Chapter 5 was dedicated to the description of the tracing capabilities of ENTRUST for the collection of evidence on their operational and configuration status, and detailed benchmarking results were provided for tracing in both High-end and Low-end devices. Specifically, in the case of High-end devices, we evaluated the impact of the **eBPF-based Tracer** when instrumenting a real-world-like binary on the operation of the CMD. The experimental results demonstrated approximately 0.3% overhead, thus inducing almost negligible performance impact, even under conditions of high syscall frequency and CPU utilisation. In Low-end devices, we investigated the feasibility of the introduction of a **power consumption metric**, and it was shown to be an interesting solution subject to limitations, such as reliance on static assumptions from datasheets, inability to capture transient behaviours, and yielding approximate results without specific hardware. However, the tracing of **static properties**, such as the validation of firmware at boot time, are simple to extract and interpret and are well suited to computationally limited Low-end CMDs.

Overall, in this deliverable, it was demonstrated that both the Blockchain Infrastructure and the tracing capabilities of ENTRUST demonstrate a high level of efficiency. The results presented here provide the basis for the evaluation of these components in D6.2 [10] in the context of the use cases. Future work will focus on further refinement of the monitoring capabilities, performance optimization, and broader integration within healthcare systems.

Appendix

MUD Profile and Trustworthiness Report

Here, we provide examples of the construction of an MUD profile in Listing 1, as well as an Trustworthiness Report in Listing 2. As detailed in Chapter 2, these are core structures whose storage is supported by the Blockchain Infrastructure of ENTRUST.

```

1 {
2   "muddata": {
3     "ietf-mud:mud": {
4       "mud-version": 1,
5       "mud-url": "https://ariamanager.com/device_uuid",
6       "last-update": "2024-02-16T11:35:25+01:00",
7       "cache-validity": 48,
8       "is-supported": true,
9       "modelname": "Aria",
10      "systeminfo": "The Aria device Current MUD File",
11      "extensions": [
12        "so-hash",
13        "integrity-fingerprint",
14        "mud-signature-certification-authority",
15        "rewire-mspl-list:mspls"
16      ],
17      "so-hash": "9
18      f86d081884c7d659a2feaa0c55ad015a3bf4f1b2b0b822cd15d6c15b0f00a08",
19      "integrity-fingerprint": "{moore_machine: {initial-state: '0', 'input-
20      alphabet: ['0', '3', '2', '1'], 'output-alphabet: ['0', '2', '1'], '
21      output-function': {'0': '0', '1': '0', '10': '2', '11': '2', '12':
22      '0', '13': '2', '14': '2', '15': '2', '16': '2', '17': '2', '18': '2',
23      '19': '2', '2': '0', '20': '2', '21': '0', '22': '0', '23': '0',
24      '24': '0', '25': '0', '26': '0', '3': '0', '4': '0', '5': '2', '6':
25      '2', '7': '2', '8': '2', '9': '1'}, 'states': ['0', '26', '17', '15',
26      '24', '19', '6', '10', '1', '8', '13', '21', '12', '14', '23', '3',
27      '5', '4', '22', '20', '7', '2', '11', '16', '25', '18', '9'], '
28      transition-function': {'0': {'0': '9', '1': '1', '2': '9', '3': '9'},
29      '1': {'0': '9', '1': '2', '2': '24', '3': '9'}, '10': {'0': '9', '1':
30      '9', '2': '11', '3': '13'}, '11': {'0': '9', '1': '9', '2': '12', '3':
31      '9'}, '12': {'0': '9', '1': '9', '2': '9', '3': '9'}, '13': {'0':
32      '14', '1': '9', '2': '9', '3': '9'}, '14': {'0': '9', '1': '9', '2':
33      '11', '3': '15'}, '15': {'0': '16', '1': '9', '2': '9', '3': '9'},
34      '16': {'0': '9', '1': '9', '2': '11', '3': '17'}, '17': {'0': '18',

```



```

'1': '9', '2': '9', '3': '9'}, '18': {'0': '9', '1': '9', '2': '11',
'3': '19'}, '19': {'0': '20', '1': '9', '2': '9', '3': '9'}, '2':
{'0': '10', '1': '3', '2': '21', '3': '9'}, '20': {'0': '9', '1': '9',
'2': '11', '3': '9'}, '21': {'0': '9', '1': '22', '2': '10', '3':
'9'}, '22': {'0': '9', '1': '23', '2': '9', '3': '9'}, '23': {'0':
'14', '1': '9', '2': '9', '3': '9'}, '24': {'0': '9', '1': '25', '2':
'9', '3': '9'}, '25': {'0': '9', '1': '22', '2': '26', '3': '9'},
'26': {'0': '9', '1': '22', '2': '9', '3': '9'}, '3': {'0': '9', '1':
'4', '2': '9', '3': '9'}, '4': {'0': '10', '1': '5', '2': '9', '3':
'9'}, '5': {'0': '5', '1': '5', '2': '6', '3': '7'}, '6': {'0': '8',
'1': '6', '2': '7', '3': '0'}, '7': {'0': '7', '1': '6', '2': '0',
'3': '6'}, '8': {'0': '5', '1': '5', '2': '8', '3': '0'}, '9': {'0':
'9', '1': '9', '2': '9', '3': '9'}}}, 'moore_alpha_maps': [{'input-map
': {'fclose@plt': '2', 'fopen@plt': '1', 'fread@plt': '0', 'fwrite@plt
': '3'}, 'output-map': {'ACCEPT': '0', 'OK': '2', 'REJECT': '1'}}, {'
input-map': {'0': 'fread@plt', '1': 'fopen@plt', '2': 'fclose@plt',
'3': 'fwrite@plt'}, 'output-map': {'0': 'ACCEPT', '1': 'REJECT', '2': 'OK'}}}],
"device-threats-list": {
  "threats-lists": {
    "threat-list": [
      {
        "name": "cve-125",
        "category": "software-vulnerability",
        "impact": "high",
        "cve": "test.url"
      }
    ]
  },
  "from-device-policy": {
    "access-lists": {
      "access-list": []
    },
    "mspl-list": {
      "mspls": [
        {
          "name": "mspl_6ccf1735-d981-4e30-87ad-34a43d5f72fa"
        }
      ]
    }
  },
  "to-device-policy": {
    "access-lists": {
      "access-list": []
    },
    "mspl-list": {
      "mspls": [
        {
          "name": "mspl_6ccf1735-d981-4e30-87ad-34a43d5f72fa"
        }
      ]
    }
  }
}

```



```

51         ]
52     }
53 }
54 },
55 "ietf-access-control-list:acls": {
56     "acl": []
57 },
58 "rewire-mspl-list:mspls": { "mspl": [
59     {
60         "name": "mspl_6ccf1735-d981-4e30-87ad-34a43d5f72fa",
61         "type": "bootstrapping-mspl-type",
62         "configuration": {
63             "capability": "bootstrapping", "rule-
64             set-configuration": {
65                 "name": "mspl_set_11868758-2e8f-4674-8a20-685ce351d3d1",
66                 "configuration-rule": [
67                     {
68                         "name": "Rule_71405326-8629-42f5-92aa-391
69                         b4de1a841",
70                         "isCNF": false,
71                         "external-data": {
72                             "priority": 500
73                         },
74                         "configuration-action":
75                         { "bootstrapping-action": {
76                             "bootstrapping-action-type": "BOOTSTRAPPING",
77
78                             "bootstrapping-model-version": "0.1",
79                             "privacy-bootstrapping-model": false
80                         }
81                     },
82                     "configuration-condition": {
83                         "bootstrapping-configuration-condition": {}
84                     }
85                 ]
86             }
87         }
88     }
89 ]
90 }
91 }
92 }
93 }

```

Listing 1: Structure of an MUD Profile

```

1 "trusteeReports": [
2     {
3         "trustworthinessReport": [

```



```

4         {
5             "appraisal": 1,
6             "claim": "configuration-integrity-verification",
7             "timestamp": "2024-07-16T13:43:05Z"
8         }
9     ],
10    "trusteeID": "Device Id 1"
11 }
12 ],
13 "evidence": {
14     "timestamp": "2024-07-16T13:43:05Z",
15     "nonce": "1
16         aa9723b221618fd81284d3ff9f3c9faa7c57826899e5e447b8cea50a01472e5",
17     "signatureAlgorithmType": "ECDSA-SHA256",
18     "signature": "3045022100
19         d4ac46d5b951700fc58a417133abc1fc310f0ddccf5636d15e41d27f228a47680
20         22023a2366880306d6b6a96f506770f57265ef81dd7267bc53706e9ba66d8beabc6",
21     "keyRef": "1"
22 }
23 });

```

Listing 2: Structure of an Trustworthiness Report

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